

SAFETY-VAC

A framework for the post-authorization safety monitoring and evaluation of the vaccines in Europe.

Study protocol for the occurrence of flares of Graves' disease, Hashimoto's thyroiditis, polyarteritis nodosa, autoimmune hepatitis, rheumatoid arthritis, psoriatic arthritis, multiple sclerosis, erythema nodosum, systemic lupus erythematosus, and ulcerative colitis using electronic healthcare data sources.

ANNEX 1

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Multiple sclerosis flare

Event Definition Form

Event: Multiple sclerosis flare-up

Outcome/covariate: Outcome

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1. Objective

The purpose of this event definition form is to establish the criteria upon which to diagnose, in clinical practice, an exacerbation or flare of Multiple sclerosis (MS), and to operationalize these criteria to capture this type of event in healthcare databases.

2. Event definition

Multiple sclerosis (MS) definition:

Multiple sclerosis (MS) is an autoimmune disorder mainly affecting young adults and characterized by destruction of myelin in the central nervous system (CNS). Pathologic findings include multiple sharply demarcated areas of demyelination throughout the white matter of the central nervous system. Clinical manifestations include visual loss, extra-ocular movement disorders, paresthesia, loss of sensation, weakness, dysarthria, spasticity, ataxia, and bladder dysfunction. The usual pattern is one of recurrent attacks followed by partial recovery, but acute fulminating and chronic progressive forms also occur (1,2).

The traditional classification of MS is divided into 4 phenotypes depending on the symptoms and onset appearance: relapsing– remitting (RR), secondary-progressive (SP), primary progressive (PP), and progressive relapsing (PR) (3,4). However, they can be classified between two main groups: relapsing (including RR, SP, and PR) and progressive (including PP, SP, and PR) forms with the major distinction being whether the subject’s disease was predominantly relapsing vs predominately progressing (5).

Flares in MS:

Flares in MS are mainly associated with disease relapse exacerbation:

- Acute or subacute objective deterioration of neurological status attributable to the disease, lasting at least 24 h in the absence of fever and followed by complete or partial resolution (7).

- A monophasic clinical episode with patient-reported symptoms and objective findings typical of multiple sclerosis, reflecting a focal or multifocal inflammatory demyelinating event in the CNS, developing acutely or sub acutely, with a duration of at least 24 h, with or without recovery, and in the absence of fever or infection. Attack, relapse, exacerbation, and (when it is the first episode) clinically isolated syndrome are synonyms (8)
- Multiple sclerosis relapses usually develop sub acutely over hours to days, reach a plateau lasting several weeks, and then gradually recover. Gross clinical recovery from relapses often appears complete in early MS; however, most relapses leave behind some aftermaths. For every clinical attack, approximately 10 ‘asymptomatic’ lesions are noted on magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). Symptomatology results from a combination of location and size— a small lesion in an eloquent area is likely to cause symptoms. Macroscopic, or MRI-visible, lesions are the tip of the iceberg; many more lesions can be seen at microscopic level and even more in deep and cortical grey matter (9).

Factors that could predispose to MS relapses (10):

- Gender
- Age
- Short MS duration
- Ethnicity
- Season
- Low level of vitamin D
- Smoking
- Stress
- Infections (Influenza A, EBV, Chlamydia, URTI)

3. Synonyms / lay terms for the event

From the NCBI description (1):

- Sclerosis, Multiple
- Sclerosis, Disseminated
- Disseminated Sclerosis
- MS (Multiple Sclerosis)
- Multiple Sclerosis, Acute Fulminating
- Multiple Sclerosis, PIRA
- Pediatric onset multiple sclerosis (POMS)

4. Diagnostic entities that may mimic the event or differential diagnosis (11):

- Cord Compression
 - o Cervical spondylosis
 - o Intrinsic or extrinsic tumor
- Hereditary
 - o Hereditary spastic paraplegia
 - o Friedreich ataxia
 - o Leukodystrophies (adrenomyeloneuropathy, Krabbe disease)
- Metabolic
 - o Vitamin B12 deficiency
 - o Phenylketonuria
 - o Copper deficiency
- Inflammatory
 - o Neurosarcoidosis
 - o Central nervous system vasculitis
- Infection
 - o Human T-cell lymphotropic virus type I (HTLV-I)
 - o Schistosomiasis
 - o Syphilis
 - o HIV
 - o Brucellosis
- Degenerative
 - o Motor neuron disease
- Toxic
 - o Lathyrism
 - o Nitrous oxide
- Vascular
 - o Dural arteriovenous malformation
 - o Cerebral autosomal dominant arteriopathy with subcortical infarcts and leukoencephalopathy (CADASIL)
 - o Paraneoplastic
- Other demyelinating conditions of childhood
 - o Acute disseminated encephalomyelitis

- Radiologically isolated syndrome
- Neuromyelitis optica spectrum disorder
- Myelin oligodendrocyte glycoprotein antibody

5. Diagnostic tests that are specific for the event

Diagnostic tests specific for MS flares are not defined, as the worsening of the disease is evaluated through the general tests used for MS (11) (12) such as:

- **CNS Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI)** [also for suspected cases]:
MRI demonstration of dissemination in space by detection of the presence of T2-hyperintense MRI lesions in four areas of the CNS, including (a) periventricular, (b) cortical or juxtacortical, and (c) infratentorial brain regions and (d) the spinal cord. The presence of at least one T2-hyperintense MRI lesion in two of these regions demonstrates dissemination in space.

6. Laboratory test that are specific for the event

Laboratory tests specific for MS flares are not defined, as the worsening of the disease is evaluated through the general tests used for MS (3) (9), such as:

- IgG index (elevated)
- Presence of IgG oligoclonal bands in Cerebrospinal fluid (CSF)
- Anti-nuclear antibody
- Vitamin B12
- Thyroid function
- Syphilis (recommended)
- Human immunodeficiency virus 1(HIV-1) serology (recommended)
- T-cell lymphotropic virus 1 and 2 serology (depending on the clinical presentation)
- Anti-aquaporin-4 and anti-myelin oligodendrocyte glycoprotein antibody screening (depending on the clinical presentation)

7. Medicinal products that are used to treat the event.

MS Treatment Schemes based on NICE Guidelines

- Clinical Isolated Syndrome (CIS)
 - Interferon (IFN)-beta 1 a (i.m.)
 - IFN-beta-1 a (s.c.)
 - IFN-beta-1 b (s.c.)
- Relapse Remitting (RRMS)
 - Mild/moderate disease
 - Dimethyl fumarate
 - Glatiramer acetates
 - Interferons4

- Teriflunomide
- (Azathioprine)
- Highly active disease
 - Pulsed therapies
 - Alemtuzumab (not approved in paediatric population)
 - Cladribine (not approved in paediatric population)
 - Ocrelizumab
 - Continuous therapies
 - Natalizumab
 - Ofatumumab
 - S1P-modulators (Fingolimod, Ozanimod, Ponesimod)
- Secondary Progressive (SPMS)
 - With relapses:
 - Cladribine
 - Interferon-b-1 b s.c.
 - Ocrelizumab
 - Ofatumumab
 - Ponesimod
 - Siponimod
 - Mitoxantrone (not recommended in paediatric population)
 - Without relapses and MRI activity
 - Siponimod
- Primary Progressive (PPMS)
 - Ocrelizumab
- Other Induction/immune reconstitution therapies (not approved in paediatric population):
 - Autologous haematopoietic stem cell transplantation
 - Cyclophosphamide

8. Procedures used to treat the event.

No procedures apply for MS flares.

9. Setting (outpatient specialist, in-hospital, GP, emergency room) where the condition will be most frequently /reliably diagnosed.

Outpatient specialist.

10. Background rates

Multiple sclerosis is more common in Europe, the United States, Canada, New Zealand, and southern Australia; it is rare in Asia, and in the tropics and subtropics (13) The estimated European mean annual multiple sclerosis incidence rate ranged from 1.1 to 7 per 100,000 population (14), with variation across regions and countries. The crude

prevalence by 100,000 shows multiple variation even within countries regions. In Italy and Malta, the prevalence goes from 15.8 - 197.8. In the British island the ranges go from 96 to 200, while in the Nordic region, the Iberian Peninsula, and Central European Countries the ranges vary from the ranges go from 20 to 200, 15 to 77, and 62 to 100 respectively (15).

The age at MS onset follows a similar pattern across different regions, with incidence low in childhood, rapidly increasing after adolescence, reaching a peak between 25 and 35 years, and then slowly declining (16,19,20) On POMS, the first attack normally happens between 11 and 13 years old (6,18).

Approximately 85%–90% of MS patients characterized by initial Clinical Isolated Syndrome (CIS) attacks present with relapsing–remitting disease: acute inflammatory demyelinating reactions, also referred to as “flares” or “exacerbations,” followed by partial or complete recovery (19). The tracked relapse rates in multiple studies ranged from 0.27 to 1.66 relapses per year (20). Pediatric MS is considerably rarer than adult-onset disease, with the highest reported incidence of 2.9/100 000 (9,21).

On pediatrics, 98% of the onset cases are RRMS while in adults is 85%. The Pediatric Onset of multiple sclerosis (POMS) shows mostly multifocal symptoms in prepubertal age and Mono focal symptoms in post pubertal age. Also, POMS have more severe and frequent relapses in comparison with the adult onset (6).

11. Diagnosis codes or algorithms are used to retrieve the event in reference literature.

- ICD-9-CM: 340, Multiple sclerosis.
- ICD-10-CM: G35, Multiple sclerosis
- SNOMED: 24700007, Multiple sclerosis

12. Code list.

A specific code list for flares is not available.

13. Algorithm proposal

Relapse algorithm:

Previous code of Multiple Sclerosis, **AND**, at least from 90 days after diagnosis (22):

Developing of new symptoms **OR** worsening of the existing ones (**excluding infections or another symptom-mimic disease code**), **OR**

- Any hospitalization or emergency room visit due MS-related conditions, **OR**
- Any MRI report with evidence of increasing on space and time (brain volume changes and changes in magnetic transfer imaging and diffusion tensor imaging), **OR**
- Changes in drug doses or changes of therapeutic scheme (see section 7, “*Medicinal products that are used to treat the event*”).

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Autoimmune hepatitis flare

Event Definition Form

Event: Autoimmune hepatitis flare

Outcome/covariate: Outcome

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1. Objective

The purpose of this event definition form is to establish the criteria upon which to diagnose an exacerbation or flare up of a preexisting autoimmune hepatitis (AIH), and to operationalize these criteria to capture this type of event in healthcare databases.

2. Event definition

Autoimmune hepatitis (AIH) definition

Autoimmune hepatitis (AIH) is a chronic liver disease in which the immune system mistakenly attacks liver cells, causing inflammation (1). It is characterized by circulating autoantibodies and elevated serum immunoglobulin G (IgG) levels. The disease may start as acute hepatitis or asymptomatic increase of liver enzymes, that can lead to the development of liver cirrhosis. In fact, one of every three adults with AIH has already developed liver cirrhosis at the time of diagnosis. It is not uncommon for AIH patients to have other extrahepatic autoimmune conditions, such as celiac disease (CD) (2) or thyroid dysfunction, among others (3). The exacerbation of autoimmune hepatitis refers to a sudden and marked increase in inflammatory activity in the liver. This exacerbation can manifest with an elevation of liver enzymes in blood tests with or without symptoms, and an elevation of immunoglobulin G, while other markers can be elevated chronically. Autoimmune hepatitis can present at any age and in all ethnic groups, but it occurs predominantly in women. For type 1 autoimmune hepatitis, the female to male ratio is 4:1, but for type 2 autoimmune hepatitis, the ratio is 10:1 (4,5).

Flares of AIH

Symptoms of exacerbation (flare) of autoimmune hepatitis are very unspecific, and vary from asymptomatic to fatigue, jaundice (yellowing of the skin and eyes), abdominal pain in the liver area, nausea, vomiting, and general discomfort. The severity of exacerbation can vary from mild to severe and may require immediate medical intervention.

Clinicians must consider the diagnosis of AIH in any patient who presents with abnormal transaminases, acute hepatitis, or acute liver failure (defined by the new onset of coagulopathy and hepatic encephalopathy). Its diagnosis is based on a series of criteria, which include clinical symptoms, laboratory findings and, more importantly, a liver biopsy (6). The 2019 American Association for the Study of Liver Diseases (AASLD) practice guideline states: “The diagnosis of autoimmune hepatitis cannot be made without liver biopsy and compatible histologic findings.” However, a diagnosis of AIH flare up should be based on an elevation of IgG and transaminases compared to the baseline/stable values for each individual patient. Other immunity parameters might be used to diagnose AIH but are not specific for a flare. AIH can progress to liver cirrhosis and end-stage liver failure if diagnosis is overlooked, and treatment is delayed (7). Most patients respond satisfactorily to treatment with corticosteroids and other immunomodulatory drugs (7). However, discontinuing immunosuppressants can lead to disease flares. The lack of adherence to the treatment may also play a role in causing flares.

Treatment

First line therapy for AIH and exacerbations:

- **Corticosteroids** [reduction of hyperactive immune response] (7, 8)
 - o With/without azathioprine or 6-mercaptopurine
 - Corticosteroids, starting dose 0.5 mg/kg of prednisolone.
 - Corticosteroids higher than 0.5 mg/kg prednisolone only in very severe acute disease (21).
 - 100 mg prednisolone daily intravenously for fulminant hepatitis with acute liver failure

In cases of **incomplete or no response to the treatment:**

- mycophenolate mofetil
- cyclosporine (more commonly applied to children)
- tacrolimus
- sirolimus
- everolimus,
- interruption of any potentially offending drug.

In cases of **intolerance, contraindications or complications to the corticosteroids:**

- budesonide can be used in patients without cirrhosis or portosystemic collaterals (23).

In acute severe autoimmune hepatitis with liver failure, lack of improvement of liver function within the first seven to 14 days of therapy has been shown to predict a poor prognosis. These are the very few patients with autoimmune hepatitis who may need emergency liver transplantation (7,22).

It is crucial for patients with autoimmune hepatitis to be closely monitored by healthcare professionals to adjust treatment as necessary and manage exacerbations effectively.

The main therapeutic goal is the induction of a full biochemical response, defined as a normalization of both transaminase and IgG concentrations. A full biochemical response is only a surrogate marker for histological remission, but its predictive power is so high that in most cases transaminase and IgG concentrations are perfectly reliable disease markers. The time needed to achieve remission can differ, and it may often take up to six months. In addition, only about two thirds of patients really achieve full biochemical remission. On the other hand, achieving a complete biochemical response not only stops progression of fibrosis but also allows for its regression, leading to an excellent long-term prognosis (7).

Children population

Unless it is a sudden and severe presentation with encephalopathy, AIH responds satisfactorily to immunosuppressive treatment whatever the degree of liver damage, with

remission rates reported up to 90%. AIH responds to immunosuppressive treatment in most cases and treatment should be instituted promptly upon diagnosis.

Conventional treatment:

- **Prednisolone** (or prednisone), 2 mg/kg/day (maximum 60 mg/day) gradually decreased during a period of 4-8 weeks in accordance with transaminase levels to a maintenance dose of 2.5-5 mg/day.

During the first 6 to 8 weeks of treatment, liver function tests should be checked weekly to allow frequent dose adjustments, avoiding severe steroid side effects.

- **Azathioprine** [added to prednisolone in the presence of serious steroid side effects, or if the transaminase levels stop decreasing on steroid treatment alone], at a starting dose of 0.5mg/kg/day.

In the absence of signs of toxicity, the dose is increased up to a maximum of 2.0–2.5mg/kg/day until biochemical control is achieved, or Azathioprine is added at a dose of 0.5 to 2mg/kg/day after a few weeks (usually 2 weeks) of steroid treatment.

- **Corticosteroids-Azathioprine combination**, as first line therapy: caution is recommended because azathioprine can be hepatotoxic, particularly in cirrhotic and severely jaundiced patients – and could result in increased side effects and higher relapse rate compared with those AIH children treated with steroid induction followed by azathioprine addition only when indicated (relapse rate 33%–36%; side effects 18%–38%).

Synonyms / lay terms of the event:

- Autoimmune hepatitis
- Autoimmune hepatitis type 1
- Autoimmune hepatitis type 2 (*more frequent in children*)
- Autoimmune hepatitis type 3
- Lupoid hepatitis
- Plasma cell hepatitis
- Autoimmune chronic active hepatitis
- Primary biliary cholangitis or primary sclerosing cholangitis variant form

3. Diagnostic entities that may mimic the event or differential diagnosis

The diagnosis of a flare of autoimmune hepatitis may be challenging because no clinical sign or symptom, nor any single biochemical or histological finding is pathognomonic of the disease (7). Without a pathognomonic test for AIH, an accurate diagnosis requires exclusion of other causes, as well as indicative clinical, serological, biochemical, and histological findings (13). Several factors, such as viral hepatitis, drug induced liver injury, alcohol hepatitis, metabolic liver diseases, should be considered in the differential diagnosis (14-16).

- Viral hepatitis: In the acute setting, it is necessary to distinguish autoimmune hepatitis from acute viral hepatitis (mainly acute hepatitis A, B, C, D, E; herpes simplex virus; Epstein-Barr virus; cytomegalovirus); or an acute exacerbation of chronic viral hepatitis (hepatitis B).
- Drug-induced liver injury: Drug-induced liver disease (DILI) can resemble autoimmune hepatitis histologically. Moreover, some drugs can develop acute inflammation similar to AIH, even with increased IgG levels and positive autoantibodies, disorder recently name DILI-AIH (17). In patients with suspected DILI or DILI-AIH, the first step is the discontinuation of the drug.
- Wilson's disease (WD): It should be considered when investigating chronic liver disease with negative viral serologies and especially in men presenting with acute hepatitis or acute liver failure (18).
- In the case of paediatric patients, other disorders may mimic an AIH, such as tyrosine metabolism disorders, glycogen storage diseases, hyperoxaluria, mytochondrial hepatopaties and other metabolic disorders (18).

4. Diagnostic tests that are specific for the event

To diagnose an AIH flare other causes need to be ruled out in the first place (19):

- Absence of viral hepatitis (6):
 - o Anti-hepatitis A virus (anti-HAV) total and IgM
 - o Hepatitis B core (HBc) IgG and IgM, hepatitis B surface Ag (HBsAg), hepatitis B surface Ab (HBsAb)

- Anti-HCV, HCV RNA [Note: One-time anti-HCV testing is now recommended by the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) for all US adults]
- Anti-hepatitis E virus (anti-HEV) IgM (and HEV RNA if anti-HEV IgM results are positive)
- Anti-herpes simplex virus (anti-HSV) IgM
- Epstein Barr Virus (EBV) DNA
- Cytomegalovirus (CMV) DNA
- Anti-varicella zoster virus (anti-VZV) IgM
- Parvovirus B19 IgG and IgM
- Absence of alcoholic hepatitis – Clinical history of alcoholism or binge consumption should be investigated and systemic OH levels checked.
- Absence of potential drugs inducing hepatotoxicity (20).

Blood tests showing an elevation of IgG and transaminases compared to the baseline/stable values for each individual patient may help diagnosing AIH flare. Other immunity parameters might be used to diagnose AIH but are not specific for a flare. Finally, liver biopsy plays a pivotal role in the debut diagnosis of an AIH or in extremely severe flare cases of unclear causes.

5. Laboratory test that are specific for the event

The diagnosis is based on a set of clinical, biochemical, serologic, and histological findings, such as high concentrations of aminotransferases, polyclonal hypergammaglobulinemia, high IgG, circulating autoantibodies, and periportal necrosis on histology (7). Laboratory findings in acute autoimmune hepatitis include the following:

- **Elevated serum aminotransferase levels** and other liver function studies compared to prior analysis / persistent elevation compared to previous analysis (albumin, bilirubin, alkaline phosphatase, international normalized ratio [INR])
- **Elevated serum immunoglobulin levels, primarily IgG**

6. Medicinal products that are used to treat the event.

General population

- Glucocorticoids (with/without azathioprine or 6-mercaptopurine)
- mycophenolate mofetil
- cyclosporine (more commonly applied to children)
- tacrolimus
- sirolimus
- everolimus
- budesonide (if without cirrhosis or portosystemic collaterals (23))

7. Procedures used to treat the event

There are no specific procedures to treat a flare of AIH, except transplantation in extreme cases.

8. Setting (outpatient specialist, in-hospital, GP, emergency room) where the condition will be most frequently /reliably diagnosed.

- Outpatient
- GP
- Outpatient specialist

9. Background rates

AIH has a global distribution and affects both sexes and all ages. This disease mainly affects females, irrespective of age, race or ethnicity, and the female-to-male ratio may be as high as 10:1 in adults (4,5,16). The reported annual incidence of AIH ranges from 0.67 cases per 100,000 persons in Israel to 2.0 cases per 100,000 persons in New Zealand (25,26). The reported prevalence of AIH ranges from 4.0 cases per 100,000 persons in Singapore to 256 cases per 100,000 persons in New Zealand and 42.9 cases per 100,000 persons in Alaska (4,27). In studies from Europe, the incidence is 0.9 to 2 per 100,000 population per year, with a prevalence of 11 to 25 per 100,000 population. Pooled annual incidences are 1.31, 1.37, and 1.00 per 100,000 persons for Asian, European, and American populations, respectively. Pooled prevalences are 12.99, 19.44 and 22.80 per 100,000 persons, respectively (28). Results from population-based studies in Denmark and in England suggest that the incidence of AIH is increasing (29). In Denmark, the incidence increased from 1.37 per 100,000 population in 1994 to 2.33 per 100,000 population in 2014 and in England the incidence doubled from 1.27 per 100,000 population to 2.56 per 100,000 population from 1997 to 2015. Although AIH can develop at any age, a bimodal peak of onset has been observed during the second and sixth decade of life (4,30). No prevalence data on autoimmune hepatitis exists for the United States (15).

According to Zen et al., 2019 (9), 25% of patients experienced a flare after a median follow-up of 57 months (range, 6-264 months) when immunosuppressants were discontinued due to remission. Another source suggests that approximately 50 percent of people remain in remission or have only mild disease activity for months to years after treatment is stopped (10,11).

Autoimmune hepatitis recurs in 8-12% of patients within the first year and 36-68% after five years from the transplantation (7,12).

AIH in children has many unique aspects compared to adults. The prevalence of AIH in children is much lower than in adults, with a frequency of ~3 cases per 100,000 people. The proportion of children with seronegative AIH is also high, ranging from 15 % to 30 % of all paediatric cases (31). Absence of autoantibody positivity makes the diagnosis of AIH more challenging. In contrast, the frequency of type 2 AIH (anti-LKM or anti-liver cytosol positivity) is much higher in children, especially those who present at a younger age with ALF or severe acute hepatitis (32).

Autoimmune polyendocrinopathy-candidiasis-ectodermal dystrophy syndrome results from mutations in the AIRE gene and up to 20% of these patients will develop AIH. Immunodysregulation polyendocrinopathy enteropathy X-linked syndrome, caused by FOXP3 mutations, results in deficient functioning of Tregs with multi-system autoimmunity, including AIH.

10. Diagnosis codes or algorithms used to retrieve the event in reference literature

Previous algorithms to diagnose AIH have been established by the Brighton Collaboration Definition and other authors (see Figures 1,3) (7,15).

Any code of AIH that is accompanied with an “exacerbation” diagnostic code or that leads to an emergency room visit or to an increase of the outpatient visits routine, may suggest a flare-up.

Figure 1. Algorithm to diagnose autoimmune hepatitis in adults and children's levels of certainty, retrieved from Kochar et al., 2024 (15)

AST: aspartate aminotransferase ALT: alanine transaminase ULN: Upper Limit of Normal IgG: Immunoglobulin G

Figure 2. Reference values for the scheme above, by Brighton Collaboration

Upper Limit of Normal (ULN) Values*	
ALT (alanine transaminase)/ SGPT (serum glutamate pyruvate transaminase)	
Normal levels (units per litre)	
Adults: 7–56 U/L	
Women: 7–35 U/L	
Men: 7–40 U/L	
Children: 5–45 U/L	
AST (aspartate aminotransferase)/ SGOT (serum glutamic oxaloacetic transaminase)	
Adults: 5–40 U/L	
Males: 10–40 U/L	
Females: 9–32 U/L	
Children: 10–40 IU/L	
Immunoglobulin G (IgG)	
Age	Normal levels (g/L/mg/dL)
Up to 2 weeks	5.0 – 17.0/ 500–1700
2 – 4 weeks	3.9 – 13.0/ 390–1300 mg/dl
1 – 3 months	2.1 – 7.7/ 210–770
3 – 6 months	2.4 – 8.8/240–880
6 – 9 months	3.0 – 9.0/ 300–900
9 – 12 months	3.0 – 10.9/300–1090
1 – 2 years	3.1 – 13.8/310–1380
2 – 3 years	3.7 – 15.8/370–1580
3 – 6 years	4.9 – 16.1/490–1610
6 –15 years	5.4 – 16.1/540–1610
16 years and older	6.0 – 16.0/600–1600

Figure 3. Algorithm to diagnose patients with possible autoimmune hepatitis (AIH), retrieved from Muratori et al., 2023 (7)

ANA=antinuclear antibodies; ELISA=enzyme linked immunosorbent assay; anti-LC1=liver cytosol antibody type 2; anti-LKM1=liver/kidney microsomal antibody type 1; pANCA=peripheral antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibodies; anti-SLA/LP=soluble liver antigen/liver-pancreas antibodies; SMA=smooth muscle antibodies

For **children**, please see the Algorithm in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Treatment algorithm for autoimmune hepatitis (AIH) for children, retrieved from ESPGHAN (24)

*Second and third-line treatments to be decided and monitored only in specialised pediatric hepatology centers. (modified from (62)).

11. Code list

To remark, no specific codes have been found to diagnose a flare of AIH. Below, related codes are presented, which might be used as part of an algorithm to detect AIH flares. Two tables have been created containing I) AIH codes (see **Table 1**) and II) Acute hepatitis codes (see **Table 2**).

Table 1. General Autoimmune Hepatitis diagnostic codes

Coding system	Code	Code name	Concept	Concept name	Tags
ICD10	K75.4	Autoimmune hepatitis	C4721555	Autoimmune hepatitis	Possible
ICD10CM	K75.4	Autoimmune hepatitis	C4721555	Autoimmune hepatitis	Possible
ICD9CM	571.42	Autoimmune hepatitis	C0241910	Autoimmune Chronic Hepatitis	Possible
ICD9CM	571.42	Autoimmune hepatitis	C0241910	Autoimmune Chronic Hepatitis	Exclude
SCTSPA	408335007	hepatitis autoinmunitaria	C4721555	Autoimmune hepatitis	Possible
SCTSPA	721713007	hepatitis autoinmunitaria, tipo 3	C4303162	Autoimmune hepatitis type 3	Possible
SCTSPA	721712002	hepatitis autoinmunitaria, tipo 2	C4303163	Autoimmune hepatitis type 2	Possible
SCTSPA	721711009	hepatitis autoinmunitaria, tipo 1	C4303164	Autoimmune hepatitis type 1	Possible
SCTSPA	1230291009	síndrome de solapamiento de colangitis biliar primaria, colangitis esclerosante primaria y hepatitis autoinmunitaria	C5680117	Primary biliary cholangitis and/or primary sclerosing cholangitis and autoimmune hepatitis overlap syndrome	Possible
SCTSPA	16098491000119109	hepatitis autoinmunitaria crónica	C0241910	Autoimmune Chronic Hepatitis	Possible
SCTSPA	1197704005	hepatitis autoinmune con autoanticuerpos negativos	C5680121	Autoantibody negative autoimmune hepatitis	Possible
SCTSPA	1197700001	várices esofágicas sangrantes por hepatitis autoinmunitaria	C5686409	Bleeding esophageal varices due to autoimmune hepatitis	Possible
SCTSPA	16098491000119109	hepatitis autoinmunitaria crónica	C0241910	Autoimmune Chronic Hepatitis	Exclude
SNOMEDCT_US	408335007	Autoimmune hepatitis	C4721555	Autoimmune hepatitis	Possible
SNOMEDCT_US	721713007	Autoimmune hepatitis type 3	C4303162	Autoimmune hepatitis type 3	Possible
SNOMEDCT_US	721712002	Autoimmune hepatitis type 2	C4303163	Autoimmune hepatitis type 2	Possible
SNOMEDCT_US	721711009	Autoimmune hepatitis type 1	C4303164	Autoimmune hepatitis type 1	Possible
SNOMEDCT_US	1230291009	Primary biliary cholangitis and/or primary sclerosing cholangitis and autoimmune hepatitis overlap syndrome	C5680117	Primary biliary cholangitis and/or primary sclerosing cholangitis and autoimmune hepatitis overlap syndrome	Possible
SNOMEDCT_US	16098491000119109	Chronic autoimmune hepatitis	C0241910	Autoimmune Chronic Hepatitis	Possible
SNOMEDCT_US	197284004	Autoimmune chronic active hepatitis	C0241910	Autoimmune Chronic Hepatitis	Possible
SNOMEDCT_US	1197704005	Autoantibody negative autoimmune hepatitis	C5680121	Autoantibody negative autoimmune hepatitis	Possible
SNOMEDCT_US	1197700001	Bleeding esophageal varices due to autoimmune hepatitis	C5686409	Bleeding esophageal varices due to autoimmune hepatitis	Possible
SNOMEDCT_US	16098491000119109	Chronic autoimmune hepatitis	C0241910	Autoimmune Chronic Hepatitis	Exclude

Coding system	Code	Code name	Concept	Concept name	Tags
SNOMEDCT_US	197284004	Autoimmune chronic active hepatitis	C0241910	Autoimmune Chronic Hepatitis	Exclude

Table 2. General Acute Hepatitis diagnostic codes

Coding system	Code	Code name	Concept	Concept name	Tags
ICD10	K72	Hepatic failure, not elsewhere classified	C0494783	Hepatic failure, not elsewhere classified	Possible
ICD10	K72.0	Acute and subacute hepatic failure	C0494784	Acute and subacute hepatic failure	Possible
ICD10CM	K76.82	Hepatic encephalopathy	C0019151	Hepatic Encephalopathy	Possible
ICD10CM	K72	Hepatic failure, not elsewhere classified	C0494783	Hepatic failure, not elsewhere classified	Possible
ICD10CM	K72.0	Acute and subacute hepatic failure	C0494784	Acute and subacute hepatic failure	Possible
ICD9CM	572.2	Hepatic encephalopathy	C0019151	Hepatic Encephalopathy	Possible
ICPC2P	D72004	Hepatitis;acute	C0267797	Acute hepatitis	Possible
SCTSPA	1197704005	hepatitis autoimmune con autoanticuerpos negativos	C5680121	Autoantibody negative autoimmune hepatitis	Possible
SCTSPA	13920009	encefalopatía hepática	C0019151	Hepatic Encephalopathy	Possible
SCTSPA	449902003	encefalopatía portal sistémica	C0019151	Hepatic Encephalopathy	Possible
SCTSPA	197284004	hepatitis activa crónica	C0520463	Chronic active hepatitis	Possible
SCTSPA	37871000	hepatitis aguda	C0267797	Acute hepatitis	Possible
SCTSPA	197271008	hepatitis aguda - no infecciosa	C0267798	Acute hepatitis - non-infective	Possible
SNOMEDCT_US	13920009	Hepatic encephalopathy	C0019151	Hepatic Encephalopathy	Possible
SNOMEDCT_US	449902003	Portal systemic encephalopathy	C0019151	Hepatic Encephalopathy	Possible
SNOMEDCT_US	37871000	Acute hepatitis	C0267797	Acute hepatitis	Possible
SNOMEDCT_US	197271008	Acute hepatitis - non-infective	C0267798	Acute hepatitis - non-infective	Possible

12. Algorithm proposal

To detect an autoimmune hepatitis flare, the following criteria should be met:

1. Diagnostic codes, which is the presence of BOTH of the following:

- Autoimmune hepatitis codes from Table 1 above, **AND**, at least 30 days after:
- Acute hepatitis codes from Table 2 above **OR** a general exacerbation code

OR

2. Diagnostic tests: presence of ALL the following:

- Autoimmune hepatitis code from Table 1 above, **AND**, at least 30 days after: IgG elevation over normal levels by age specified in the reference values for the scheme in **Figure 4** by Brighton Collaboration, **AND**
- Transaminase elevation x1.5-5 times from the basal values of the patient in two consecutive measurements within the 30 days prior to the diagnostic code, compared with baseline patients' numbers **OR** transaminitis diagnostic codes (i.e., R74.01)

OR

3. Visits:

- Autoimmune hepatitis code from Table 1 above, **AND**, at least 30 days after: Increase of the frequency of outpatient visits to ≤ 2 months in between visits, **OR**, Hospitalization or emergency room visit due to AIH as primary diagnosis.

OR

4. Treatments. Presence of:

- Autoimmune hepatitis code from Table 1 above **AND**, at least 30 days after: If the patient is ≥ 18 years of age: New start of glucocorticoids, , mycophenolate mofetil, tacrolimus, sirolimus or everolimus (not prescription or dispensing present in the previous 30 days)
- If the patient is < 18 years of age: New start of glucocorticoids, antiTNF, rituximab or cyclosporin (not prescription or dispensing present in the previous 30 days)

As the AIH flare is an exclusion diagnoses after ruling out other etiologies, after applying the previous algorithm we need to exclude the following. **NOT**:

- Diagnostic code of viral hepatitis in a time window of 30 days apart from any of the inclusion points above

OR

- Diagnostic code of alcohol hepatitis in a time window of 30 days apart from any of the inclusion points above

OR

- Presence of prescriptions or dispensing of any of the drugs with a DILrank ≥ 3 in the DILrank (20), in a time window of 30 days apart from any of the inclusion points above

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Erythema nodosum flare

Event Definition Form

Event: Erythema nodosum flare

Outcome/covariate: Outcome

Version: 0.1

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1. Objective

The purpose of this event definition form is to establish the criteria upon which to diagnose, in clinical practice, an exacerbation or flare of erythema nodosum, and to operationalize these criteria to capture this type of event in healthcare databases.

2. Event definition

Erythema nodosum (EN) definition

Erythema nodosum (EN) is a type of panniculitis, an inflammatory disorder affecting subcutaneous fat. It is a delayed-type hypersensitivity reaction that most often presents as erythematous tender nodules on the anterior shins. Less commonly, they affect the thighs and forearms (1,2). Common triggers for EN include infection, drugs, pregnancy, malignancy, and inflammatory conditions, such as sarcoidosis or gastrointestinal diseases. However, many cases are idiopathic (3,4). EN may be also associated with various systemic diseases, such as VEXAS, Löfgren syndrome, bacterial infections (mainly streptococcal infections), autoimmune diseases (like sarcoidosis), and some drug reactions. In summary, EN can occur secondary to a wide variety of conditions (5-8).

Flares in EN

EN has few known complications and lesions usually resolve spontaneously. A rare complication is encapsulated fat necrosis, or 'mobile encapsulated lipoma'. The exacerbation of erythema nodosum refers to a sudden and intense increase in symptoms associated with this dermatological condition. It manifests through an inflammatory response of the subcutaneous fat which leads to painful red nodules on the skin, commonly on the legs. The nodules are slightly raised and typically 2 to 5 cm in diameter. Less frequently, lesions can coalesce into plaques or arise on other areas such as the ankles, thighs, arms, buttocks, calves, or face (14). The nodules develop over several days and may follow a prodrome of fatigue, fever, malaise, arthralgias, or upper respiratory infection symptoms by one to three weeks (14). Joint swelling, erythema, or pain may accompany the skin manifestations. Nodules typically resolve spontaneously without scarring within eight weeks of presentation. Secondary bruising, also known as "erythema contusiformis," often occurs during resolution (8). Residual hyperpigmentation may take weeks to months to resolve.

The prognosis for EN is good, with most cases resolving spontaneously or with supportive care over days to 1–6 weeks by turning from a bright red to a yellow–brown or green–bluish discoloration, resembling bruises. Coexistence of lesions in different stages of evolution can be seen in the same patient. The nodules heal without ulceration, scarring, or atrophy, and recurrences are not uncommon (1). Relapses may occur in up to one-third of cases or in cases triggered by chronic, underlying disease. Relapses usually can be rapidly controlled with treatments for EN and kept infrequent through aggressive management of the triggering condition (8).

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3. Synonyms / lay terms for the event

- Panniculitis
- Erythematous nodule/s
- Septal panniculitis
- Subcutaneous nodules
- Encapsulated fat necrosis
- Meischer's radial granuloma
- Nodular vasculitis
- Löfgren syndrome (not a direct synonym, but includes erythema nodosum)

4. Diagnostic entities that may mimic the event or differential diagnosis

A range of causes of panniculitis should be considered in a patient with subcutaneous nodules, especially if lesions are not located on the legs, there is ulceration, or symptoms last longer than eight weeks. Panniculitis can be predominantly septal (inflammation between lobules) or lobular (inflammatory cells within subcutaneous fat lobules). Mixed septal and lobular inflammation can occur.

Nodules due to predominantly septal panniculitis include:

- Various forms of scleroderma
- Medium vessel vasculitis, for example, cutaneous polyarteritis nodosa in which there are tender subcutaneous nodules associated with ulceration, necrosis, livedo racemosa, fever, joint pain, myalgia, and peripheral neuropathy
- Alpha-1 antitrypsin deficiency: genetic deficiency in functional alpha-1 antitrypsin can result in erythematous, tender, subcutaneous nodules or plaques that frequently ulcerate and drain.
- Necrobiosis lipoidica
- Eosinophilic panniculitis
- Rheumatoid nodule

Nodules due to predominantly lobular panniculitis include:

- Connective tissue disease (eg, panniculitis associated with cutaneous lupus erythematosus)
- Erythema nodosum leprosum (type 2 lepra reaction due to leprosy)
- Pancreatic panniculitis in which subcutaneous nodules may become ulcerated or fluctuant. Laboratory tests reveal elevated lipase, amylase and trypsin levels
- Traumatic panniculitis
- Nodular vasculitis (erythema induratum, Bazin's disease) in which ulcerated, draining nodules affect the posterior calves

- Lipodermatosclerosis, which is a consequence of venous insufficiency
- Infection of the subcutaneous fat with bacteria, mycobacteria or fungi, which may cause ulcerated, fluctuant, and draining abscesses
- Malignant subcutaneous infiltrates, including paraneoplastic syndromes

5. Diagnostic tests that are specific for the event

No specific diagnostic tests are available for EN flares. However, EN is primarily a clinical diagnosis confirmed by laboratory tests and histopathology. There are no laboratory abnormalities specific to EN. However, patients may have laboratory abnormalities related to the underlying disease:

- Clinical exploration
- Deep incisional or excisional skin biopsy: the characteristic histologic finding in EN is a septal panniculitis without vasculitis. Lobular inflammation should not be the predominant finding

Other unspecific EN diagnostic tests are:

- Pregnancy test (referral to a gastroenterologist or hematologist, as associated condition)
- Throat swab and anti-streptolysin O and streptodornase serology (streptococcal infection)
- Viral serology (preferably two samples at four-week intervals)
- Stool culture and evaluation for ova and parasites in patients with gastrointestinal symptoms
- Mantoux test or QuantiFERON gold (tests for tuberculosis)
- Urinalysis
- Serum aminotransferases, lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), creatinine, protein electrophoresis, and immunoglobulins should complete the routine blood workup.
- Celiac screening should also be done, even without other symptoms/signs of CD.
- Among imaging, the chest X-ray is still mandatory as it can reveal tuberculosis, sarcoidosis, other pulmonary infections, and lymphoma.
- Abdomen ultrasound could be helpful if gastrointestinal manifestations are present.
- Other investigations should be chosen case-by-case, for instance, a pregnancy test must be done in all sexually active subjects, and angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) should be measured in the suspicion of sarcoidosis.

6. Laboratory test that are specific for the event

There are no laboratory abnormalities specific to EN and its flares.

However, patients may have laboratory abnormalities related to the underlying disease (15).

- Complete blood count (infectious and inflammatory causes)

- Erythrocyte sedimentation rate and/or C-reactive protein (elevation is a sign of systemic disease and widespread inflammation)

7. Medicinal products that are used to treat the event

EN usually resolves spontaneously within several weeks. Treatment often is not necessary, particularly for mild cases. Reasons for treatment include significant discomfort, inability to bear weight, extensive skin involvement, and/or chronic or recurrent disease.

- **Non-steroidal Anti-inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs)** [management of pain, first line]:
 - o Ibuprofen: > 12 years and 40kg of weight, 400 800 mg every four to six hours as needed (maximum 3,200 mg per day)
 - o Naproxen: 250 to 500 mg twice daily as needed (maximum 1250 mg per day)
 - o Indomethacin (for adults, 25 to 50 mg every 8 to 12 hours as needed [maximum 200 mg per day]) is an alternative for patients who do not respond adequately to other NSAIDs but is used less often due to a greater frequency of adverse effects (16).

Severe EN treatment:

- systemic corticosteroids (1 mg/kg daily until resolution of erythema nodosum) [prescribed if infection, sepsis, and malignancy have been ruled out, or, in case of underlying bowel disease].
 - o prednisone (20 mg taken every morning for 7 to 10 days).
- **Intralesional corticosteroid injection(9,17)** [second-line treatment, if systemic glucocorticoids cannot be tolerated; 10-20 mg/mL].
- **Oral potassium iodide as a supersaturated solution** (SSKI, 400–900 mg/day) may be prescribed. If improvement does not occur within two to three weeks, treatment is discontinued. For patients who respond to potassium iodide, the treatment continues for two to three weeks after resolution.

Chronic EN treatment:

- **Colchicine** (1-2 mg/day) [management of pain and severe or chronic EN, second line]
- **Hydroxychloroquine**
- **Dapsone**

A review published in 2022 (15), suggests the following options for pediatric patients:

- **Intralesional and/or systemic corticosteroids** may be considered for severe cases, and eventually used with caution after exclusion of infectious disease; a dose of 0.5–2 mg/kg/day of prednisone for a period of 1–2 months had variable success in one pediatric case series.

- **Oral liquid or chewable tablets of ibuprofen** are recommended in infants. Dosages by weight are: 50mg for children up to 8kg, 80 mg up to 10 kg, 100mg up to 16 kg, 150mg up to 21kg, 200mg up to 27kg, 250mg up to 32kg, 300mg up to 43kg, and above 40-43kg, equivalent dosages than adults can be used.
- More aggressive treatment also may be tailored to disease-specific regimens in case of secondary EN:
 - o **steroids** used in combination with **hydroxychloroquine, cyclosporin A, or biologic agents** (anti-interleukin 12/23, Vedolizumab) have been used to treat autoimmune disease-associated EN (18,19).

For hydroxychloroquine, colchicine and dapsone there is no evidence available for paediatric patients.

Treatment of EN in pregnant women is complicated by the fact that many of the medications used in EN have not been proven safe for use in pregnancy. Restricting management to nonpharmacologic interventions, such as bed rest, leg elevation, and compression is preferred (20).

A summary of the treatment strategy of EN is summarized in the Table below:

Table 3 Treatment of erythema nodosum in adults and pregnant women, retrieved from Pérez-Garza DM., et al.¹

Treatment	Mechanism of action	Dosage	Comments/pregnancy risk category
Compression bandage and limb elevation	Edema and pain relief	-	-
Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs	Anti-inflammatory	-	Caution in patients with IBD as they may trigger a flare-up or worsen an ongoing acute disease episode
Indomethacin		100–150 mg daily	
Naproxen		500–1000 mg daily	Pregnancy category C
Potassium iodide	Anti-inflammatory, neutrophil chemotaxis and suppression of toxic radicals	300–900 mg daily	Use with caution in patients with thyroid diseases Pregnancy category D
Colchicine	Anti-inflammatory, decreases neutrophil chemotaxis and degranulation	1–2 mg daily	Consider in patients with Behçet syndrome Pregnancy category C
Dapsone	Anti-inflammatory, inhibits neutrophil myeloperoxidase and chemotaxis	50–75 mg daily	Consider in recurrent and recalcitrant lesions Consider G6PD deficiency screening Pregnancy category C
Hydroxychloroquine	Anti-inflammatory	200 mg twice daily	Consider in chronic and recurrent cases Pregnancy category C (not formal)
Intralesional corticosteroids	Anti-inflammatory	-	Consider in recalcitrant nodules Pregnancy category C
Triamcinolone acetonide		5 mg/mL	
Oral corticosteroids	Anti-inflammatory	-	

Treatment	Mechanism of action	Dosage	Comments/pregnancy risk category
Prednisone		40–60 mg daily	Consider in severe disease Exclude an underlying infectious etiology before its use Pregnancy category D in first trimester, C in second and third trimester
Tetracyclines	Anti-inflammatory; suppresses leukocyte chemotaxis and reactive oxygen species	-	Consider for recalcitrant lesions Pregnancy category D
Minocycline		100 mg twice daily	
Tetracycline		500 mg twice to four times daily	
Erythromycin	Anti-inflammatory	500 mg four times daily	Consider for recalcitrant lesions Pregnancy category B
TNF- α inhibitors	Anti-inflammatory, inhibits TNF- α	-	Screen for latent tuberculosis, HBV, HCV, and HIV infection before use Consider in patients with IBD Pregnancy category B
Etanercept		25–50 mg twice weekly tapering to 25–50 mg weekly	
Adalimumab		40 mg every 2 weeks	
Infliximab		5 mg/kg in weeks 0, 2, and 6	
Thalidomide	Anti-inflammatory, thought to be through inhibition of TNF- α release and activity	No specific data	Consider in patients with IBD Pregnancy category X
Cyclosporine A	-	No specific data	Consider in patients with IBD

G6PD glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase, *HBV* hepatitis B virus, *HCV* hepatitis C virus, *HIV* human immunodeficiency virus, *IBD* inflammatory bowel disease, *TNF* tumor necrosis factor

8. Procedures to treat the event

- Leg elevation.
- Rest.
- Venous compression therapy (if tolerable), such as stockings providing low-grade compression (8 to 15 mmHg or 15 to 20 mmHg stockings). Elastic bandages may be of benefit to patients unable to tolerate or apply stockings.
- Wound debridement.

9. Setting (outpatient specialist, in-hospital, GP, emergency room) where the condition will be most frequently /reliably diagnosed.

- GP
- Outpatient
- Specialist visits

10. Background rates

No specific background rates about EN flares are reported. Overall, EN occurs in approximately 1-5 per 100,000 persons, varying upon the different geographic areas and the various associated triggering diseases (21). A higher incidence (12–14 cases/100,000) was reported in Scandinavia (22).

In adults, it is more common among women, with a male-to-female ratio of 1:3 to 1:6 (2,23). In children up to the age of 12 years, the sex ratio is 1:1 (24). Peak incidence occurs in persons between second to fourth decades of life, although erythema nodosum can occur at any age (25,26). In contrast, it is rare in pediatric age and exceptional in children before the age of 2 years (21).

In north-western Spain, the annual incidence rate of biopsy-proven EN for the population aged 14 years and older was 52 cases/ 1 million and the incidence was higher in the first half of the year when streptococcal infections are more frequent (3).

EN can be distinguished between a primary form, also called idiopathic, which represents a quote variable among 23% (24) up to 55% (26), and a secondary one ranging from 47% (5) to 77% (24). Some authors found a lower rate of idiopathic EN in adults, as Porges et al. who reported 9% (22) and García-Porrúa et al. who reported 37% (3). Other authors found 17–72% of EN being idiopathic, while 28–68% being a secondary subtype (25,27). Drugs are another frequent etiologic factor of EN and have been identified as the cause of EN in 2.9–5% of patients. Pregnancy represents the etiologic cause in 2–6% of patients. According to the literature 32–72% of EN cases remain with an unknown etiology (1).

In children, it can be primary/idiopathic in 23–55% cases, or secondary in 47–77% cases (15).

11. Diagnosis codes or algorithms used to retrieve the event in reference literature

- **ICD10:** L52 Erythema nodosum
- **ICD9-CM:** 695.2 Erythema nodosum

12. Codelist

Coding system	Code	Code name	Concept	Concept name	Tags
ICD10	L52	Erythema nodosum	C0014743	Erythema Nodosum	Possible
ICD10CM	L52	Erythema nodosum	C0014743	Erythema Nodosum	Possible

Coding system	Code	Code name	Concept	Concept name	Tags
ICD9CM	17.1	Erythema nodosum with hypersensitivity reaction in tuberculosis	C0014744	Tuberculous erythema nodosum	Possible
ICD9CM	17.1	Erythema nodosum with hypersensitivity reaction in tuberculosis, unspecified	C0014744	Tuberculous erythema nodosum	Possible
ICD9CM	695.2	Erythema nodosum	C0014743	Erythema Nodosum	Possible
SCTSPA	961007	eritema nudoso, forma aguda	C0263644	Erythema nodosum, acute form	Narrow
SCTSPA	2028007	eritema indurado	C0014741	Erythema Induratum	Possible
SCTSPA	11354005	tuberculosis cutánea indurativa	C0014741	Erythema Induratum	Possible
SCTSPA	32861005	eritema nudoso	C0014743	Erythema Nodosum	Possible
SCTSPA	51696001	lipogranulomatosis subcutánea de Rothmann y Makai	C0406598	Lipogranulomatosis subcutanea of Rothmann and Makai	Possible
SCTSPA	74610006	eritema nudoso tuberculoso	C0014744	Tuberculous erythema nodosum	Possible
SCTSPA	76097009	eritema nudoso migratorio	C0030331	Panniculitis, Subacute Nodular Migratory	Possible
SCTSPA	78223000	coccidioidomycosis con eritema nudoso	C0276671	Coccidioidomycosis with erythema nodosum	Possible
SCTSPA	181225007	síndrome de adenopatía hilar bilateral	C0340164	Lofgrens syndrome	Possible
SCTSPA	238675007	eritema nudoso por sarcoidosis	C0406390	Sarcoidosis-induced erythema nodosum	Possible
SCTSPA	238676008	síndrome de Lofgrens	C0340164	Lofgrens syndrome	Narrow
SCTSPA	240360007	eritema nodosum por Yersinia	C0343388	Yersinia erythema nodosum	Possible
SCTSPA	297940005	eritema nudoso medicamentoso	C0574713	Drug-induced erythema nodosum	Narrow
SCTSPA	402968000	eritema nudoso causado por Bacteria	C1274379	Erythema nodosum caused by Bacteria	Possible
SCTSPA	402969008	eritema nudoso causado por género Streptococcus	C1274380	Erythema nodosum caused by Genus Streptococcus	Possible
SCTSPA	402970009	eritema nudoso debido a Yersinia enterocolitica	C1274381	Erythema nodosum caused by Yersinia enterocolitica	Possible
SCTSPA	702449004	síndrome de autoinflamación, lipodistrofia y dermatosis	C1850568	Nakajo syndrome	Possible
SCTSPA	703966004	paniculitis aguda	C3875565	Acute panniculitis	Possible
SCTSPA	860801002	eritema nudoso debido a infección fúngica sistémica	C5395903	Erythema nodosum due to systemic fungal infection	Possible
SNOMEDCT_US	961007	Erythema nodosum, acute form	C0263644	Erythema nodosum, acute form	Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	2028007	Erythema induratum	C0014741	Erythema Induratum	Possible
SNOMEDCT_US	11354005	Tuberculosis cutis indurativa	C0014741	Erythema Induratum	Possible
SNOMEDCT_US	32861005	Erythema nodosum	C0014743	Erythema Nodosum	Possible
SNOMEDCT_US	51696001	Lipogranulomatosis subcutanea of Rothmann and Makai	C0406598	Lipogranulomatosis subcutanea of Rothmann and Makai	Possible
SNOMEDCT_US	74610006	Tuberculous erythema nodosum	C0014744	Tuberculous erythema nodosum	Possible
SNOMEDCT_US	76097009	Erythema nodosum migrans	C0030331	Panniculitis, Subacute Nodular Migratory	Possible

Coding system	Code	Code name	Concept	Concept name	Tags
SNOMEDCT_US	78223000	Coccidioidomycosis with erythema nodosum	C0276671	Coccidioidomycosis with erythema nodosum	Possible
SNOMEDCT_US	181225007	Bilateral hilar adenopathy syndrome	C0340164	Lofgrens syndrome	Possible
SNOMEDCT_US	238675007	Sarcoidosis-induced erythema nodosum	C0406390	Sarcoidosis-induced erythema nodosum	Possible
SNOMEDCT_US	238676008	Lofgrens syndrome	C0340164	Lofgrens syndrome	Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	240360007	Yersinia erythema nodosum	C0343388	Yersinia erythema nodosum	Possible
SNOMEDCT_US	297940005	Drug-induced erythema nodosum	C0574713	Drug-induced erythema nodosum	Narrow
SNOMEDCT_US	402968000	Erythema nodosum caused by Bacteria	C1274379	Erythema nodosum caused by Bacteria	Possible
SNOMEDCT_US	402969008	Erythema nodosum caused by Genus Streptococcus	C1274380	Erythema nodosum caused by Genus Streptococcus	Possible
SNOMEDCT_US	402970009	Erythema nodosum caused by Yersinia enterocolitica	C1274381	Erythema nodosum caused by Yersinia enterocolitica	Possible
SNOMEDCT_US	702449004	Nakajo-Nishimura syndrome	C1850568	Nakajo syndrome	Possible
SNOMEDCT_US	703966004	Acute panniculitis	C3875565	Acute panniculitis	Possible
SNOMEDCT_US	860801002	Erythema nodosum due to systemic fungal infection	C5395903	Erythema nodosum due to systemic fungal infection	Possible

13. Algorithm proposal

To detect an erythema nodosum (EN) flare, the following criteria should be met:

Any code of erythema nodosum **OR** Subcutaneous nodules **OR** Encapsulated fat necrosis **OR** Meischer's radial granuloma, **OR** Nodular vasculitis **AND**, at least 60 days after:

- Code of Acute erythema nodosum code **OR**
- panniculitis **OR**
- Erythematous nodule/s **OR**
- Septal panniculitis **OR**

- Löfgren syndrome, **OR**
- Upper respiratory infection (followed by any erythema nodosum code within 3 weeks in case it was not present before), **OR**
- Debridement procedure, **OR**
- Hospitalization or emergency room visit due to EN as primary diagnosis, **OR**
- Initiation of one of the following treatments (after a 60-days dispensing/prescription gap):
 - If adults (>17 years-old):
Compression bandage and limb elevation, ionsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, indomethacin, naproxen, potassium iodide, colchicine, dapsone, hydroxychloroquine, intralesional corticosteroids, triamcinolone acetonide, oral corticosteroids, prednisone, tetracyclines, minocycline, tetracycline, erythromycin, TNF- α inhibitors, etanercept, adalimumab, infliximab, thalidomide, cyclosporine A.
 - If children (<18 years-old):
intralesional and/or systemic corticosteroids, oral liquid or chewable tablets of ibuprofen, steroids used in combination with hydroxychloroquine, cyclosporin A, or biologic agents (anti-interleukin 12/23, Vedolizumab).

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Hashimoto's thyroiditis flare

Event Definition Form

Event: Hashimoto's thyroiditis flare-up

Outcome/covariate: Outcome

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1. Objective

This event definition form aims to provide an operationalizable definition to detect a flare-up of Hashimoto's thyroiditis in electronic healthcare record databases to conduct epidemiologic research.

2. Event definition

Hashimoto's thyroiditis definition

Hashimoto's thyroiditis, also called chronic lymphocytic or autoimmune thyroiditis, is an autoimmune disease in which thyroid cells are destroyed through cell and antibody-mediated immune processes. The pathophysiology of Hashimoto's thyroiditis involves the formation of antithyroid antibodies that attack the thyroid tissue, causing progressive fibrosis (1). This condition is characterized by the presence of high serum thyroid autoantibodies, Goiter, and hypothyroidism.

Flares in Hashimoto's thyroiditis

A Hashimoto's flare-up is a period of worsening and intense hypothyroidism symptoms (2). In addition, Hashimoto's flare can be characterized by a hyperthyroid state.

3. Synonyms / lay terms for the event

- Disease, Hashimoto
- Chronic Lymphocytic Thyroiditis
- Chronic Lymphocytic Thyroiditides
- Lymphocytic Thyroiditides, Chronic
- Lymphocytic Thyroiditis, Chronic
- Thyroiditides, Chronic Lymphocytic
- Thyroiditis, Chronic Lymphocytic
- Hashimoto's Struma
- Hashimoto's Struma

- Hashimoto's Syndrome
- Hashimoto Syndrome
- Hashimoto's Syndromes
- Hashimoto's Syndrome
- Syndrome, Hashimoto's
- Syndromes, Hashimoto's
- Hashimoto's Disease
- Disease, Hashimoto's
- Hashimoto's Disease
- Chronic autoimmune thyroiditis
- Autoimmune thyroiditis

4. Diagnostic entities that may mimic the event or differential diagnosis

Radiation treatment (3), Graves' disease, and nontoxic nodular Goiter (4).

5. Diagnostic tests that are specific for the event

Not Available (NA)

6. Laboratory test that are specific for the event

NA

7. Medicinal products that are used to treat the event

- Levothyroxine

8. Procedures used to treat the event

NA

9. Setting (outpatient specialist, in-hospital, GP, emergency room) where the condition will be most frequently /reliably diagnosed.

- GP
- out-patient specialist
- in-hospital
- emergency room

10. Background rates

HT is one of the most common thyroid diseases. The reported incidence goes from 0.3 to 1.5 cases per 1000 persons. It is 4 to 10 times more common in women than men. Although the disease may occur in teenagers or young women, it more often develops in women ages 30 to 50. HT prevalence is higher in patients with myasthenia gravis and systemic sclerosis (5) than other populations. HT prevalence in childhood ranges around 1-2%. (5,6).

11. Diagnosis codes or algorithms used to retrieve the flare in reference literature

N/A

12. Code list

There are no specific codes to detect flares of HT. The ICD-9 code usually adopted for HT is 245.2, the ICD-10 code is E06.3, and the SNOMED code is 21983002.

For SNOMED-based code lists, there are general codes to detect a disease flare-up:

Coding system	Code	Code name	Concept	Concept name
SCTSPA	230993007	desmejoría	C0332271	Worsening pattern
SCTSPA	263855007	recaída	C0035020	Relapse
SCTSPA	255318003	curso recidivante	C0205336	Relapsing course
SCTSPA	264498007	Cyclical relapsing		
SCTSPA	303359000	episodio de recidiva	C0580821	Relapse episode
SCTSPA	414482001	indicación de recaída	C1532287	Indication for relapse
SCTSPA	390772001	deterioro del estado	C1279889	Deterioration of status
SCTSPA	409053002	se espera que se deteriore	C1443541	Expected to deteriorate
SCTSPA	774093002	Escala de Deterioro General	C4537573	Global Deterioration Scale
SCTSPA	774094008	nivel de la Escala de Deterioro General	C4751527	Global Deterioration Scale level
SCTSPA	774095009	evaluación con la Escala de Deterioro Global	C4751528	Assessment using Global Deterioration Scale
SCTSPA	231877006	peor	C1457868	Worse
SNOMEDCT_US	230993007	Worsening	C0332271	Worsening pattern
SNOMEDCT_US	263855007	Relapse phase	C0035020	Relapse
SNOMEDCT_US	255318003	Relapsing course	C0205336	Relapsing course
SNOMEDCT_US	264498007	Cyclical relapsing		
SNOMEDCT_US	303359000	Relapse episode	C0580821	Relapse episode

SNOMEDCT_US	414482001	Indication for relapse	C1532287	Indication for relapse
SNOMEDCT_US	390772001	Deterioration of status	C1279889	Deterioration of status
SNOMEDCT_US	444861000124106	Slightly worse		
SNOMEDCT_US	445111000124102	Much worse		
SNOMEDCT_US	409053002	Expected to deteriorate	C1443541	Expected to deteriorate
SNOMEDCT_US	774093002	Global Deterioration Scale	C4537573	Global Deterioration Scale
SNOMEDCT_US	774094008	Global Deterioration Scale level	C4751527	Global Deterioration Scale level
SNOMEDCT_US	774095009	Assessment using Global Deterioration Scale	C4751528	Assessment using Global Deterioration Scale
SNOMEDCT_US	231877006	Worse	C1457868	Worse

13. Algorithm proposal

HT diagnosis (through diagnosis codes) **AND**, at least 90 days after (7):

- Identification of a code indicating a relapse of symptoms (only for SNOMED-based codes), **OR**
- Start of Levothyroxine use after 90 days of first HT diagnosis and evidence of no use of this medication since the first-disease diagnosis (re-start)., **OR**
- Any emergency room visit or hospitalization for HT cause as primary diagnosis at any time.

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Systemic lupus erythematosus flare

Event Definition Form

Event: Systemic lupus erythematosus flare-up

Outcome/covariate: Outcome

Version: 0.2

Status: Draft

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1. Objective

The aim of this event definition form is to establish a definition for an outcome that can be implemented for the detection of a flare-up of SLE in electronic healthcare record databases.

2. Event and flare-up definition

Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) definition

Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) is a chronic, relapsing, inflammatory, and often febrile multisystemic autoimmune disease of connective tissue, primarily characterized by involvement of the skin, joints, kidneys, and serosal membranes. Its etiology remains unknown, though it is believed to stem from a breakdown in the regulatory mechanisms of the autoimmune system. The disease manifests through a diverse array of systemic dysfunctions, elevated erythrocyte sedimentation rate, and the presence of lupus erythematosus (LE) cells in the blood or bone marrow (1). It is characterized by periods of increased disease activity (flares) followed by periods of disease remission (2).

Flares in SLE

SLE flare-up is a measurable increase in disease activity in one or more organ systems involving new or worse clinical findings/laboratory measurements, that is usually accompanied by a change or an increase in the treatment, involving stronger agents or higher dosages (3). There are also some SLE disease activity surveys to define a SLE flare-up: SLEDAI-2K, the British Isles Lupus Assessment Group (BILAG) 2004 index and Safety of Estrogens in Lupus National Assessment (SELENA) Flare Index. *Goetz et al* developed a claims-based algorithm identifying SLE flare-up using a linked claims-electronic medical record (EMR) dataset. A SLE flare-up during a given month was defined as an increase of four or more points over that patient's median SLEDAI-2K score during the first 12 months of follow-up (5).

Ding et al. investigated the impact of SLE flare-up on clinical and economic outcomes, categorizing patients into three groups based on the most severe flare experienced during the baseline period: no flares, mild, or moderate/severe (2).

3. Synonyms / lay terms for the event

- Lupus Erythematosus Disseminatus

- Libman-Sacks Disease
- Disease, Libman-Sacks
- Libman Sacks Disease
- Juvenile-onset systemic lupus erythematosus (jSLE)

4. Diagnostic entities that may mimic the event or differential diagnosis

It should be considered as differential diagnosis, adverse drug reactions, infection, metabolic or endocrine disorder, and malignancy (6).

5. Diagnostic tests that are specific for the event

No diagnostic tests are specific for SLE flare-up beyond the ones already used for the LSE disease, which are known to have good sensitivity and often specificity, such as:

- ultrasound techniques (e.g., echocardiography, musculoskeletal ultrasound)
- magnetic resonance
- computer tomography
- X-ray, biopsy (e.g., kidney, skin).

6. Laboratory test that are specific for the flare/event

General tests used for SLE are:

- ANA + anti-dsDNA
- ANA + other ENAs
- ANA + cardiolipin Ab
- ANA + lupus anticoagulant
- ANA + >1 C3/C4.

The following laboratory tests are suggestive of a SLE flare-up:

- anti-dsDNA variation (no absolute titer) > fluctuations of anti-dsDNA could be associated with sawtooth-shaped trend in serum antibody levels (increase $\geq 50\%$, decrease $\geq 50\%$, and new increase $\geq 50\%$) within a six-month timeframe (7).
- ESR
- CRP
- anti-Smith/RNP.

7. Medicinal products that are used to treat the flare-up

List of LSE Medicinal products (2) (8):

- **Non-steroidal Anti-inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs)** [management of inflammation]:
 - Ibuprofen
 - Naproxen

- **Corticosteroids:**
 - Prednisone
 - Methylprednisolone

- **Antimalarial drugs:**
 - Hydroxychloroquine
 - Cloroquine
 - Quinacrine

- **Immunosuppressant drugs:**
 - Methotrexate
 - Azathioprine
 - Mycophenolate mofetil
 - Mycophenolic acid
 - Cyclosporine
 - Cyclophosphamide,
 - Tacrolimus,
 - Leflunomide
 - Voclosporin

- **Biologic response modifiers (bDMARDs):**
 - Rituximab
 - Belimumab
 - Anifrolumab

SLE flares treatments:

Therapeutic strategies for SLE flares encompass:

- oral glucocorticoids dose escalation
- injectable glucocorticoids
- initiation of a new prescription for a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID)
- antimalarial

- immunosuppressants
- biologics
- hospitalization with SLE as the primary diagnosis for a minimum of 7 days
- and/or hospitalization with primary diagnoses related to SLE flare for 7 days or more

Additionally, for severe flares, pulse therapy with intravenous methylprednisolone at a dosage of 250–1000 mg per day for 1–3 days is recommended (4).

8. Procedures used to treat the event

In case of severe SLE the following procedures are recommended (9):

- Hemodialysis
- Peritoneal dialysis
- Hemodiafiltration,
- Kidney transplantation
- Plasmapheresis
- Immunoabsorption

9. Setting (outpatient specialist, in-hospital, GP, emergency room) where the condition will be most frequently /reliably diagnosed.

- In- and out-patient visits
- hospitalization
- emergency room visits
- Specialist visits

10. Background rates

No specific rates for SLE flares are reported. However, different studies widely reported the incidence and prevalence of SLE.

The global SLE incidence and newly diagnosed population were estimated to be 5.14 (1.4 to 15.13) per 100,000 person-years and 0.40 million people annually, respectively. In women, the values were 8.82 (2.4 to 25.99) per 100 000 person-years and 0.34million people annually, while in men, the estimates were 1.53 (0.41 to 4.46) per 100 000 person-years and 0.06 million people annually, respectively. Regarding prevalence, the global SLE prevalence and affected population were estimated to be 43.7 (15.87 to 108.92) per 100,000 persons and 3.41 million people, respectively. Specifically, in women, the values were 78.73 (28.61 to 196.33) per 100 000 persons and 3.04million people, while in men the estimates were 9.26 (3.36 to 22.97) per 100 000 persons and 0.36million people, respectively (10).

In young populations, jSLE is characterized by disease onset before the age of 18 and affects approximately 15–20% of SLE patients (8). The incidence of jSLE ranges between 0.36 and 2.5 per 100,000 children, with a prevalence of 1.89–34.1 per 100,000. Compared to adult-onset SLE, jSLE is more aggressive, with higher disease activity and medication burden (including corticosteroids and other immunosuppressive drugs), leading to increased morbidity and mortality. It presents with more severe organ manifestations, greater damage at diagnosis, and a higher incidence of renal, cardiovascular, and neuropsychiatric involvement. Overall standardized mortality rates are higher in SLE compared to the general population (SMR 2.2 across all ages), with patients under the age of 18 experiencing approximately three times higher mortality rates than normal (SMR 6.5).

11. Diagnosis codes or algorithms used to retrieve the flare in reference literature

Algorithm for determining SLE flare severity, adapted from Garris et al., 2013 (11).

Mild SLE flare

Initiation of any of the following:

- hydroxychloroquine or another anti-malarial
- belimumab
- an oral corticosteroid with prednisone-equivalent dose of ≤ 7.5 mg/day
- non-immunosuppressive therapy (NSAIDs, androgens).
- Treatment was considered to be ‘initiated’ if there were no filled prescriptions for that class of medication in the 60 days prior to the medication fill.

Length of flare: 30 days. However, if a flare of higher severity (moderate or severe) occurs during those 30 days, the length of the flare was limited to the time between the start of the mild flare and the start of the higher-severity flare.

Moderate SLE flare

a. Initiation of any of the following:

- an oral corticosteroid with prednisone-equivalent dose >7.5 mg/day but ≤ 40 mg/day,
- immunosuppressive therapy, with the exception of cyclophosphamide.

Treatment was considered to be ‘initiated’ if there were no filled prescriptions for that class of medication in the 60 days prior to the medication fill. For oral corticosteroids, if the patient had a prior fill within 60 days, treatment was considered initiated if the prior fill was for a prednisone-equivalent dose less than or equal to 7.5 mg/day, **OR**

b. A claim for an emergency room visit with a primary diagnosis of SLE (710.0x) with no inpatient admission within 1 day, **OR**

c. A claim for an emergency room or office visit with a primary or secondary diagnosis for a specified SLE-related condition. If the diagnosis occurred during an office visit, the condition was required to be new, defined as no claims with this diagnosis during the previous 60 days. If the condition occurred in an emergency room visit, no inpatient admission within 1 day following the emergency room visit was allowed.

Length of flare: 30 days. However, if a severe flare occurred during those 30 days, the length of the flare was limited to the time between the start of the moderate flare and the start of the higher-severity flare. If the flare was initiated by a hospitalization, or a hospitalization occurred during the middle of the flare, and the hospitalization lasts beyond 30 days, the length of the flare was still set at 30 days.

Severe SLE flare

a. Initiation of any of the following:

- an oral corticosteroid with prednisone-equivalent dose >40 mg/day,
- Cyclophosphamide, rituximab, cyclosporin, voclosporin.

For corticosteroids, if the patient had a prior fill within 60 days, treatment was considered initiated if the prior fill was for a dose less than or equal to 40mg/day. For cyclophosphamide, each prescription was counted as a new prescription if the prior fill or administration was more than 100 days earlier, **OR**

b. Admission for an inpatient hospital stay with a primary diagnosis of SLE (710.0x), **OR**

c. Admission for an inpatient hospital stay with a primary diagnosis for a specified SLE-related condition.

For flares based upon a hospitalization, the start date of the flare was the date that the patient was admitted to the hospital, unless the patient was admitted to the emergency room (with any diagnosis) during the previous day; if patients had an emergency room admission the day prior to the hospitalization, the date of the emergency room admission was considered to be the start date of the flare. Note that only visits to an emergency room site were considered under this definition; visits to urgent care or outpatient clinics were not included.

Length of SLE flare: 30 days.

For flares, specified SLE-related conditions included the conditions listed for the disease severity algorithm, plus the following conditions: arthritis/arthralgia, dry eye/tear film insufficiency, rash, low white blood cell count (leukopenia, neutropenia, lymphocytopenia), lymph node enlargement, myalgia/myositis, urticarial.

Pediatric flares from Weiss et al, 2007 (12)

For the flare definition:

- a. The addition of, or an increase in, the dose of corticosteroids, **AND/OR**
- b. The addition of an immunosuppressive medication (cyclophosphamide, cyclosporine, azathioprine, or mycophenolate mofetil) within 2 weeks of the prior office visit. If an immunosuppressive medication was added as a steroid-sparing agent, and not because of active disease, then that visit was not considered a flare visit.

Length of flare: the post-flare visit was defined as the visit where the physician assessment read “resolution of flare” or “stable” after a minimum of 2 weeks without defined flare.

12.Code list

Table 1. List of ICD-9, ICD-10 and SNOMED codes for SLE diagnosis (5, 9, 11, 13)

ICD-9	ICD-10	SNOMED
		4676006
		11013005
		25380002
		33110008
		36402006
	M32.1	52042003
	M32.8	55464009
	M32.9	68815009
	M32	69746005
	M320	73286009
710.0x	M3210	76521009
695.4	M3211	95332009
37334	M3212	95408003
	M3213	95644001
	M3214	156450004
	M3215	196138005
	M3219	197608009
	M328	201435004
		201437007
		201438002
		230307005
		239887007
		239889005
		239890001
		273862004
		307755009
		309762007
		397856003
		402865003
		403486000
		417303004
		698694005
		72181000119109
		295101000119105
		295111000119108
		295121000119101
		201439005
		203784000
		308751000119106

13. Algorithm proposal

Diagnosis of SLE, **AND**, at least 90 days after:

- Any initiation of high dose glucocorticoids, NSAIDs, (mild flare), **OR**
- Any initiation of immunosuppressive agents (i.e., methotrexate, azathioprine, mycophenolate mofetil, leflunomide), or monoclonal antibody (anifrolumab, belimumab) (moderate flare), **OR**
- Any initiation of or switching to any Disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs (DMARDs) (i.e., conventional nonbiologic/ synthetic, targeted synthetic, or biologic) (moderate flare), **OR**
- Initiation of rituximab, cyclosporine, voclosporin (severe flare), **OR**
- Initiation of cyclophosphamide (severe flare), **OR**
- Hospitalization and emergency room visit due to SLE, due to SLE-related condition as primary diagnosis (severe flare).

In pediatric population:

Diagnosis of SLE **AND** (at least 30 days after) initiation of immunosuppressive agents.

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Ulcerative Colitis flare

Event Definition Form

Event: Ulcerative Colitis flares

Outcome/covariate: Outcome

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1. Objective

This event definition form aims to provide an operationalizable definition to detect a flare-up of Ulcerative colitis (UC) in electronic healthcare record databases to conduct epidemiologic research.

2. Event definition

Ulcerative colitis (UC) definition

Ulcerative colitis (UC) is a type of inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) that is characterized by continuous and diffuse inflammation which is limited to the colonic mucosa and extends proximally from the rectum (1). It is considered a chronic immune-mediated inflammatory disorder of the colon that is hypothesized to be related to exposure to environmental risk factors leading to inappropriate immune responses to enteric commensal microbes in genetically susceptible individuals (2)(3)(4). The disease develops most often in the second or third decade of life. The classic symptoms are bloody diarrhea, abdominal pain, fecal urgency, and/or tenesmus (1).

Classification by severity is mostly based on the description of Truelove and Witts made in 1955:

- **UC in clinical remission (S0):** No symptoms of UC.
- **Mild UC (S1):** in the classic description of disease activity by Truelove and Witts, this was defined as four or fewer bloody stools daily, lack of fever, pulse of less than 90 beats/min, hemoglobin of 105 g/L or greater and erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) of less than 30 mm/h. A similar definition was given in the practice guidelines for management of UC recently published by the American College of Gastroenterology (ACG): four or fewer stools daily (with or without blood), no systemic signs of toxicity and a normal ESR.
- **Moderate UC (S2):** Truelove and Witts defined this as the state between mild and severe. The ACG guidelines defined moderate disease as more than four stools daily but with minimal signs of systemic toxicity.
- **Severe UC (S3):** This was defined as the passage of at least six bloody stools daily, pulse of at least 90 beats/min, temperature of at least 37.5°C, hemoglobin of less than 105 g/L and ESR of at least 30 mm/h. The ACG guidelines defined severe colitis as at least six bloody stools daily and evidence of toxicity (fever, tachycardia, anemia or elevated ESR)

- **Fulminant UC.** This is subclassification integrated by the American College of Gastroenterology. These patients include more than 10 bowel movements daily, continuous bleeding, toxicity, abdominal tenderness and requirement for blood transfusion, colonic dilation and/or abdominal films (8).

For young patients, the Pediatric Ulcerative Colitis Activity Index (PUCAI) has been adopted as a response to a less invasive and more accurate technic to assess UC disease. This method uses 6 topics assigned with a score depending on the severity: Abdominal Pain (0 – 10), rectal bleeding (0 – 30), stool consistency (0 – 10), number of stools per day (0 – 15), nocturnal stools (0-10) and activity level (0 – 10). A total score from 35 to 54 is considered a moderate disease, while upper this score is severe and under can be mild or none (14).

Flares in UC:

UC relapse is defined as flare up of symptoms in a patient who is in clinical remission. Typically, these patients have rectal bleeding, an increase in stool frequency and abnormal mucosa at sigmoidoscopy (24,25). The relapse is considered early if it occurs within 3 months after achieving remission with previous therapy. The pattern of relapse could be infrequent (less than or equal to 2 episodes/year), frequent (more than twice per year), or continuous (persistent symptoms of active UC without a period of remission) (24). On children, disease activity should be monitored at every visit (especially after 3 months of remission), utilizing PUCAI score, and treatment should be revisited when there is change of 10 points in the scoring. Also, colonoscopy is recommended before any change of drug scheme and/or when the calprotectin has marked high levels in routinary checking (10).

The previous definition should be differentiated from the Steroid-dependent patients. These patients who are unable to discontinue corticosteroids without experiencing a symptomatic relapse are steroid dependent, one form of chronically active UC. The term “steroid-dependency” applies to individuals whose disease flares below a particular dose of steroids and remains asymptomatic only if they continue this medication.

3. Synonyms / lay terms for the event (26)

- Idiopathic Proctocolitis
- Ulcerative Colitis
- Colitis Gravis
- Inflammatory Bowel Disease
- Ulcerative Colitis Type
- Ulcerative Pancolitis
- Ulcerative Rectosigmoiditis
- Ulcerative Proctitis

4. Diagnostic entities that may mimic the event or differential diagnosis.

(27,28)

- Infectious colitis: bacterial, viral, fungal (histoplasmosis), mycobacterial, and Clostridium difficile
- Ischemic colitis
- Segmental colitis associated with diverticulitis.
- Radiation-induced colitis or proctitis
- Medication-induced colitis (non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, oncologic immunotherapy, antiCD20 monoclonal antibodies
- Crohn's disease
- Sexually transmitted diseases (particularly in patients with proctitis who practice anal intercourse): Chlamydia trachomatis, Neisseria gonorrhoeae, herpes, and syphilis.
- If predominant symptom is diarrhea and not rectal bleeding, coeliac disease, microscopic colitis, lactose or other food intolerances, and irritable bowel syndrome.

5. Diagnostic tests that are specific for the event

Diagnostic tests specific for UC flares are not defined, as the worsening of the disease is evaluated through the general tests used for UC, (6) (29) such as:

- **Endoscopy**, it is mainly used for
 - o assessing disease extent, severity of inflammation, excluding Crohn's disease (flexible sigmoidoscopy or Ileocolonoscopy), and surveillance
- **Histology**, at least two biopsies from each bowel segment
- **Imaging:**
 - o **Abdominal X-ray**
 - o **Cross sectional imaging: CT/MRI**

6. Laboratory test that are specific for the event

Laboratory tests specific for UC flares are not defined, as the worsening of the disease is evaluated through the general tests used for UC (29) such as the following:

- **Blood tests:**
 - o Full blood count Urea and electrolytes
 - o C-reactive protein
 - o Vitamin D and bone profile

- Haematinics
- Liver biochemistry

Anaemia, thrombocytosis, low vitamin D and raised inflammatory markers. In contrast to adult UC, high sensitivity (hs)-CRP was not suitable to differentiate between remission and relapse in children with normal standard CRP (48).

- **Stool cultures:**

- Clostridioides difficile toxin assay MC&S [Should be negative if UC, but infections such as C difficile can co-exist]

- **Fecal calprotectin:**

A level of 50–100 µg/g has a high negative predictive value of 98–99% in the diagnosis of IBD. Levels >135-170 µg/g predicts endoscopic and histological activity in clinical quiescent colitis (Hart et al, 2020). On children, calprotectin value of > 275 µg/g can be useful to predict relapses or worsening of disease (Diamanti et al, 2008).

7. Drugs used to treat the event.

List of UC Medicinal products (30):

Activity: mild/moderate UC,

- Proctitis [adults and children]:
 - 1st treatment: 5-ASA (Mesalamine, 5 –Amino salicylic) p.r. (rectal)
 - No response to 5-ASA rectal: Add 5-ASA p.o. (oral) and/or Prednisolone p.o.
 - Remission: Return to 5-ASA exclusive
- Left-sided colitis:
 - 1st treatment: 5-ASA p.o. + p.r
 - No response: Add Budesonide MMX (multimatrix) till remission.
 - Remission: return to 5-ASA Exclusive
- Extensive colitis:
 - 1st treatment: 5-ASA p.o. + p.r
 - No response: Prednisolone p.o or steroids IV
 - Remission: return to 5-ASA Exclusive

Activity: Severe / fulminant UC,

- Prednisolone systemic, intravenous (IV)
- If no response: classified and treat as follow:

- Steroid-dependent course:
 - Azathioprine /6-Mercaptopurine (MP) [adults and children]
 - TNF antibodies:
 - infliximab [adults and children]
 - adalimumab
 - golimumab
 - Ustekinumab
 - Vedolizumab
 - Tofacitinib
- Steroid – refractory course:
 - –TNF antibodies, see left
 - Ustekinumab
 - Vedolizumab
 - Cyclosporine/tacrolimus
 - Tofacitinib
- Targeted synthetic DMARDs (ts-DMARDs):
 - Janus kinase (JAK) inhibitors
 - Upadacitinib
 - Filgotinib (JAK 1)
- If no response to the above: continue with surgery procedure

For pediatric patients, Oral 5-ASA compounds are the first line of induction and maintenance on Mild-moderate UC, being combined oral and rectal more effective than a monotherapy. In rectal therapy, 5-ASA is preferred over steroids. As second line of treatment for mild-moderate UC not responding to 5-ASA and first line for high moderate UC, oral steroids should be considered. IV steroids are recommended for severe UC. Infliximab (IFX) should be considered chronically active or steroid-dependent UC, uncontrolled by 5-ASA and thiopurines, for both induction and maintenance of remission. Adalimumab [EL4, adults EL4] or golimumab [EL4, adults EL3] could be considered in those who initially respond but then lose response or are intolerant to IFX (Harbord, 2017).

8. Procedures used to treat the event.

Treatment options in complication courses of the disease, in children in case should be individualized (30).

- Colectomy
- Proctocolectomy

Restorative proctocolectomy with ileal pouch-anal anastomosis (IPAA) (28)

- Three-stage procedure (subtotal colectomy with ileostomy first) is recommended for patients with acute severe colitis, treated with high-dose steroids, or recent anti-TNF therapy, severe malnutrition, or IBDU (10).

9. Setting (outpatient specialist, in-hospital, GP, emergency room) where the condition will be most frequently /reliably diagnosed.

Outpatient specialist

10. Background rates

No sex predominance exists in UC (Loftus, 2004 & Bernstein 2006). The peak age of disease onset is between 30-40 years old. 20% to 30% of patients with UC and CD disease have the onset of their symptoms below the age of 18, although diagnosis is often delayed. The highest incidences of ulcerative colitis have been reported in northern Europe (24.3 per 100 000), Canada (19.2 per 100 000), and Australia (17.4 per 100 000). Prevalence rates are highest in Europe (505 per 100 000), Canada (248 per 100 000), and the USA (214 per 100 000) (6,28,31–37). The incidence of pediatric onset UC, which constitutes roughly 15% to 20% of all UC, ranges at 1 to 4/100,000/year in most North American and European regions (38).

Overall, 20% to 25% of patients with UC experience severe exacerbations requiring hospitalization for prompt medical treatment, and colectomy is considered if medical treatments fail. Several reports have shown that the morbidity related to patients with acute severe UC (ASUC) was considerable, with a 30% to 40% risk for colectomy after one or more severe exacerbations, and that 10% to 20% of these patients' required colectomy at their first admission. Meanwhile, from 1999 to 2005 Korean ASUC cohort indicated a better short- and long-term prognosis for ASUC in Koreans than in Caucasians. A recent ASUC cohort study of an Italian group demonstrated that 1-, 3-, and 5-year colectomy-free survival were 93.5%, 81.5%, and 79.4%, respectively, and approximately 50% of patients with ASUC required additional treatment or hospitalization due to relapse. Thus, careful follow-up even after induction of remission of patients with ASUC is crucial (39).

11. Diagnosis codes or algorithms are used to retrieve the event in reference literature.

- ICD-10-CM: K51 Ulcerative colitis
- SNOMED CT: 64766004 Ulcerative colitis

- HPO : 0100279 , Ulcerative Colitis
- UMLS : C0009324 , Ulcerative colitis
- MSH: D003093 , Ulcerative colitis
- OMIM: 266600 , Inflammatory Bowel Disease

12. Code list

No specific codes are available for flare-up of UC.

13. Algorithm proposal

A code UC **AND**, at least 90 days after:

- Identification of a code indicating a relapse of symptoms (only for SNOMED-based codes), **OR**
- Rectal bleeding (through diagnosis codes), **OR**
- Code for Anemia (<10.5g/dl), **OR**
- Any blood transfusion performed, **OR**
- Apheresis of any component of blood, **OR**
- Endoscopy/ colonoscopy / CT/ MRI with report of tissue status worsening, **OR**
- Any increase in doses or change of medication scheme, **OR**
- Hospitalization or emergency room visit due to UC as primary diagnosis, **OR**
- Any surgical procedure due to complications of UC
 - Colectomy
 - Proctocolectomy
 - Restorative proctocolectomy with ileal pouch-anal anastomosis (IPAA)

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Grave's disease flare

Event Definition Form

Event: Grave's disease flare up

Outcome/covariate: Outcome

Version: 0.2

Status: Draft

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1. Objective

This event definition form aims to provide an operationalizable definition to detect a flare-up of Graves' disease (GD) in electronic healthcare record databases to conduct epidemiologic research.

2. Event definition

Grave's disease (GD) definition

Grave's disease (GD) is a common form of hyperthyroidism with a diffuse hyperplastic goiter. It is an autoimmune disorder that produces thyrotropin-receptor antibodies (TRAb) against the thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH) receptor. These autoantibodies activate the TSH receptor, thereby stimulating the thyroid gland and hypersecretion of thyroid hormones. These autoantibodies can also affect the eyes (Grave's ophthalmopathy) and the skin (Grave's dermopathy) (1).

Flares in GD

The terms flare up and relapse are used interchangeably. A flare up/relapse of GD can be defined as both, the worsening of hyperthyroidism symptoms and an increase in thyroid hormones above the expected range in patients with GD who are currently undergoing treatment (e.g. taking antithyroid drugs (ATD)), and the re-occurrence of hyperthyroidism symptoms and the increase in thyroid hormones in patients with GD after completion of treatment (ATDs stopped, radioiodine or surgery).

The occurrence of GD relapse is strongly dependent on the therapeutic strategy implemented at diagnosis time. Up to 50% of patients who started treatment with an ATD may experience a relapse, compared to permanent hypothyroidism options (15% for radioactive iodine therapy and 10% for thyroidectomy)(2) Furthermore, important risk factors to relapse are the presence of orbitopathy, smoking, larger thyroid volume and biochemically more severe disease (3,4). Studies have shown that the long-term remission rate of GD in children after ATD therapy is about 17–33% (5,6), which is lower than that of adults, and they are more likely to relapse after ATD withdrawal.

3. Synonyms / lay terms for the event

- Basedow Disease
- Disease, Basedow
- Exophthalmic Goiter
- Exophthalmic Goiters
- Goiters, Exophthalmic
- Goiter, Exophthalmic
- Hyperthyroidism, Autoimmune
- Basedow's Disease
- Basedows Disease
- Disease, Basedow's
- Thyrotoxicosis
- Thyroid crisis
- Thyroid storm

4. Diagnostic entities that may mimic the event or differential diagnosis

- Toxic nodular goitre (Plummer's Disease),
- Induced thyroiditis (viral or drug induced)
- Gestational hyperthyroidism
- Gestational trophoblastic disease
- Iodine-induced hyperthyroidism
- Toxic adenoma
- Thyrotoxicosis factitial (7).

5. Diagnostic tests that are specific for the event

Not Available (NA)

6. Laboratory test that are specific for the event

- Antibodies to the TSH receptor (TRAb)
- After drug withdraw, decreasing serum TSH and increasing free T3 and T4 levels (also valid for children (8)).

7. Medicinal products that are used to treat the event

Clinically relevant flare up episodes requires the control of symptoms with either drugs, procedures, or both. For instance, it may be necessary to scale up the doses of ATDs and beta-blockers.

- **Antithyroid drugs (ATD):**
 - o Propylthiouracil
 - o Carbimazole
 - o Methimazole
- **Beta-blockers:**
 - o Propranolol
 - o Atenolol

8. Procedures used to treat the event

- Radioactive iodine therapy
- Thyroidectomy (total or near-total)

9. Setting (outpatient specialist, in-hospital, GP, emergency room) where the condition will be most frequently /reliably diagnosed.

- In- and out-patient visits
- hospitalization
- emergency room visits
- GP

10. Background rates

No specific rates for GD flares are reported. However, it is reported the incidence of GD in iodine-sufficient regions, which is 20–30 cases per 100 000 per year, with a peak in the third to fifth decades of life, and a female to male ratio of 5–6:1(7).

11. Diagnosis codes or algorithms used to retrieve the event in reference literature.

NA

12. Code list

There are no specific codes to detect GD flares.
Any code of thyroid storm can be used for flares identification.

13. Algorithm proposal

Graves' disease diagnosis, **AND**, at least 90 days after:

- Identification of a code indicating a relapse of symptoms (only for SNOMED-based codes), **OR**
- Evidence of ATDs prescription/dispensing in patients having a period of 90 days of no drug exposure (relapse), **OR**
- Evidence of radioactive iodine ablation > 90 days after last ATDs, **OR**
- Thyroidectomy (procedure) > 90 days after last ATDs prescription/dispensing, **OR**
- Thyroidectomy (procedure) 3 years after last radioactive iodine ablation session (9), **OR**
- ATD treatment in a patient previously exposed to radioactive iodine ablation 3 years ago, **OR**
- Any code of Thyroid storm, **OR**
- Any emergency room visit or hospitalization for rheumatologic cause as primary diagnosis at any time.

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Psoriatic arthropathies flare

Event Definition Form

Event: Psoriatic arthropathies flare up

Outcome/covariate: Outcome

Version: 0.2

Status: Draft

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1. Objective

This event definition form aims to provide an operationalizable definition to detect a flare-up of Psoriatic arthropathies (PsA) in electronic healthcare record databases to conduct epidemiologic research.

2. Event definition

Psoriatic arthropathies, or psoriatic arthritis (PsA) is a type of inflammatory arthritis associated with psoriasis, whose main clinical manifestations are peripheral arthritis, dactylitis, enthesitis and axial involvement. It is characterized by the presence of HLA-B27-associated spondyloarthropathy and the absence of Rheumatoid Factor (RF). Psoriatic arthritis occurs in approximately 30% of patients with psoriasis (PsO)(1), and typically, skin involvement precedes the onset of PsA by several years (about 5-10 years). Less commonly, both conditions may debut simultaneously, and in fewer cases, PsA may develop first followed by PsO.

PsA flare-up could be broadly considered as a period of worsening in disease activity, with a significant effect on patients' quality of life (4).

Across the 17.6% of PsA patients who achieve disease remission (no inflamed joints for 12 months), 52% experienced flares after 12 months on average (2). Whereas patients achieving low disease activity are reported to be around 33%, and approximately 10% of them had flares, unrestrictedly of the therapy (3).

Juvenile psoriatic arthritis (juvenile idiopathic arthritis (JIA)) is the most common rheumatic disease in childhood and an important cause of short- and long-term disability (5). Some JIA patients may recover spontaneously, with studies reporting over 50% of patients being in clinical remission of medication, 30 years after disease onset. Previous studies have reported that the risk of disease flare increases in girls with positive autoantibodies, multiple joint involvements at the time of diagnosis, and disease severity (6–9). Various biomarkers are defined for this purpose (10,11). However, an explicit model effective in predicting the risk of flare is not yet reported (12).

3. Synonyms / lay terms for the event

- Psoriasis, Arthritic
- Arthritic Psoriasis
- Psoriatic Arthritis
- Psoriasis Arthropathica
- Psoriatic Arthropathy
- Arthropathies, Psoriatic
- Arthropathy, Psoriatic

- Psoriatic Arthropathies
- Juvenile idiopathic arthritis
- Juvenile psoriatic arthritis

4. Diagnostic entities that may mimic the event or differential diagnosis

- Rheumatic arthritis and other
- Non-psoriatic inflammatory arthritis:
 - o septic arthritis
 - o enteropathic arthritis
 - o ankylosing spondylitis
 - o calcium pyrophosphate crystal deposition (CPPD) disease
 - o gout
 - o complex regional pain syndrome.

5. Diagnostic tests that are specific for the event

No diagnostic tests are specific for PsA flare-up beyond the ones already used for the PsA disease, such as:

- Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI)
- Ultrasound
- X-rays
- Computed tomography (CT) scanning
- Positron emission tomography (PET) scan
- Bone scan
- Skin biopsy

6. Laboratory test that are specific for the event

No laboratory tests are specific for PsA flare-up beyond the ones already used for the PsA disease:

- Erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR or sed rate) [inflammation, blood test]
- C-reactive protein (CRP) [inflammation, blood test]:
- Human Leukocyte Antigen B27 (HLA-B27) is a protein found on the surface of white blood cells. It helps your immune system tell the difference between your own cells and harmful invaders. An abnormal result could mean that you have an autoimmune disease like PsA, ankylosing spondylitis or inflammatory bowel disease.

To exclude the diagnosis of rheumatoid arthritis (RA), doctors may request these RA tests:

- Rheumatoid factor (RF) [antibody, positivity only for RA, blood test]
- Anti-cyclic citrullinated peptide antibody [antibody, positivity only for RA, blood test].

7. Medicinal products that are used to treat the event

List of PsA Medicinal products:

- **Non-steroidal Anti-inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs)** [symptomatic cases]
- **Corticosteroids:**
 - o Local glucocorticoids injections [for mono-articular flares]
 - o Systemic glucocorticoids [for oligo- or poly-articular flares]
- **Disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs (DMARDs)** [depending on the disease activity, alone or in combination (13); long-term use prescription to reduce flares risks]:
 - **Conventional synthetic disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs (csDMARD):**
 - o Methotrexate [mainly for frequent infections] (14).
 - o Leflunomide
 - o Sulfasalazine
 - **Biological disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs (bDMARD):**
 - o Targeting TNF:
 - Adalimumab
 - Certolizumab
 - Etanercept
 - Infliximab
 - Golimumab
 - o Targeting IL-12/23:
 - Ustekinumab
 - o Targeting IL-17A:
 - Ixekizumab
 - Secukinumab
 - o Targeting IL-17A/F:
 - Bimekizumab
 - o Targeting IL-23-p19:
 - Gusulkumab
 - Risankizumab
 - o Targeting CTLA4:
 - Abatacept

- Targeted synthetic disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs (tsDMARD):
 - Targeting PDE4:
 - Apremilast [mainly for frequent infections] (14).
 - Targeting JAK:
 - Tofacitinib
 - Upadacitinib

PsA flares treatments:

- Local glucocorticoid injections [mono-articular flares]
- Systemic glucocorticoid [oligo- or poly-articular flares]
- increased dosage of DMARDs [oligo- or poly-articular flares]
- any change in baseline treatment [oligo- or poly-articular flares]

8. Procedures used to treat the event

- Local glucocorticoid injections (for monoarticular flares)
- joint debridement
- joint aspiration
- arthroplasty (joint replacement)
- arthrodesis
- synovectomy
- resection (e.g., foot, toe).

9. Setting (outpatient specialist, in-hospital, GP, emergency room) where the condition will be most frequently/reliably diagnosed.

- In- and out-patient visits
- hospitalization
- emergency room visits

- GP

10. Background rates

The incidence rate of PsA has been reported between 3.4 to 8.5 per 100,000 (15,16). The prevalence of PsA flares in the adult population has been reported between 7.5 to 10% (17).

In children and adolescents, studies in developed countries have reported a JIA prevalence that varies between 16 and 150 per 100,000 (5). For JIA relapse rate after discontinuation of bDMARDs, either abruptly or following tapering, were 40–48%, 36.8–45.0% and 60–78% at 6, 8 and 12 months, respectively. Total relapse rate ranged from 26.3% to 100%, with mean time to relapse (TTR) of 2 to 8.4 months, the median TTR between 3 to 10 months. All studies stated a good response after restart of therapy after flare (18).

JIA subtype, type of bDMARD, concomitant methotrexate use, treatment duration, tapering method, age, sex, and time in remission could not conclusively be related to relapse rate or TTR. However, some studies reported a positive correlation between flare and antinuclear antibodies' positivity, younger age at disease onset, male sex, disease duration and delayed remission, which were not confirmed in other studies.

11. Diagnosis codes or algorithms used to retrieve the event in reference literature.

No specific codes of PsA flare-up are available, only those for general PsA disease (19).

12. Code list

No specific code list to identify a flare of PsA.

13. Algorithm proposal

Diagnosis of PsA (using diagnosis codes) **AND**, at least after 90 days:

- Any initiation of Non-steroidal Anti-inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs), **OR**
- Any initiation of a corticosteroids, **OR**
- Any initiation of or switching to any Disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs (DMARDs) (see table 1), **OR**
 - a. Conventional Nonbiologic or Synthetic DMARDs (csDMARDs)
 - b. Targeted synthetic DMARDs (ts-DMARDs)
 - c. Biologic response modifiers (bDMARDs)

- Increasing dosages of any DMARDs, **OR**
- Adding any DMARDs or systemic glucocorticoids to preexisting treatment, **OR**
- Switching from local glucocorticoid injections (mono-articular flare) to systemic glucocorticoids (oligo-/poly-articular flare), **OR**
- Any hospitalization or emergency room visit for rheumatologic cause as primary diagnosis.

14. Limitations

Missing information about medicines dosage may impact accurately on identifying cases of PsA flares.

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Rheumatoid Arthritis flare

Event Definition Form

Event: Rheumatoid Arthritis flare up

Outcome/covariate: Outcome

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1. Objective

This event definition form aims to provide an operationalizable definition to detect a flare-up of Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) in electronic healthcare record databases to conduct epidemiologic research.

2. Event definition

Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA) definition

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a chronic inflammatory disease characterized by joint swelling, joint tenderness, and destruction of synovial joints, leading to severe disability and premature mortality. The cause of RA is unknown. Given the presence of autoantibodies, such as rheumatoid factor (RF) and anti-citrullinated protein antibody (ACPA) (tested as anti-cyclic citrullinated peptide [antiCCP]), which can precede the clinical manifestation of RA by many years, RA is considered an autoimmune disease. Autoimmunity and the overall systemic and articular inflammatory load drive the destructive progression of the disease. (1,2). Damages cannot generally be reversed, so early diagnosis and treatment are very important. Extra-articular manifestations may develop, and various tissues and organ systems can be affected (i.e., rheumatoid nodules, rheumatoid vasculitis,

interstitial lung disease). Cardiovascular disease is a common consequence of chronic inflammation and the primary cause of death in people with RA. In RA patients, the risk of infection is elevated not only due to the disease itself but also particularly because of the immunosuppressive agents used in its treatment (1,3).

Flares in RA

Defining disease worsening or flare in RA is likely represented by composite changes in multiple variables rather than worsening in only a single characteristic. Flares of inflammatory disease activity and of pain may often not coincide. Among the most widely utilized indices are the Clinical Disease Activity Index (CDAI), the Disease Activity Score using 28 joint counts (DAS28), and the Simplified Disease Activity Index (SDAI). These indices offer a comprehensive assessment by capturing crucial disease aspects in a single score, facilitating treatment decisions and monitoring of disease progression (4).

RA flare occurs with any worsening of disease activity that would, if persistent, in most cases lead to initiation or change of therapy; and a flare represents a cluster of symptoms of sufficient duration and intensity to require initiation, change or increase in therapy as cannot be self-managed (5–7).

The 2022 EULAR recommendations for the management of rheumatoid arthritis (9) states that therapy should be adapted or changed if insufficient improvement (less than 50% of disease activity) is seen after 3 months from initiation (see Figure 1). The definition of “short-term” therapy refers to 3 months (12 weeks) duration.

Flares Duration

The length of time spent by the patient in a flare state may span from a few days to several weeks. The length and frequency of flares are associated with radiographic progression and deterioration of physical function, an increase in CVD risk, and a reduction in physical activity (10).

- Transient reported flares duration: <14 weeks
- Constant flares duration: 14 weeks
- Constant flares and increased risk of comorbidities duration: 6-12 weeks
- Major flares duration: > 6months

RA complications (1)

- Joint inflammation with radiographic damage, progressive deformity, and functional disability.
- Carpal tunnel syndrome, cervical myelopathy
- Anemia and Felty syndrome (for seropositive RA)
- Secondary form of Sjögren syndrome, scleritis, inflammatory eye disease, Rheumatoid vasculitis

- Pleuritis, bronchiolitis, pulmonary embolism, Interstitial lung disease (ILD- some patients may present with ILD before developing joint inflammation but being RA seropositive)
- Coronary artery disease (CAD), atherosclerosis, peripheral vascular disease, pericarditis, vasculitis (inflammation of the blood vessels)
- Insulin resistance and diabetes mellitus (also associated with glucocorticoids therapy)
- Lymphoma (higher incidence of non-Hodgkin lymphoma and diffuse B-cell lymphoma)
- Premature death (associated also with treatment)
- Serious infections (associated also with treatment)
- Osteopenia and osteoporosis (also associated with glucocorticoids therapy).
- venous thromboembolic disease (also associated with TNF inhibitor therapy and JAK inhibitors)
- Accelerated rheumatoid nodulosis (11).

RA and RA Flares Risk Factors:

- Genetic susceptibility (HLA-DRB1)
- Sex (female at higher risk than males)
- Hormonal and reproductive factors (12) and hormones Therapy (13)
- Silica exposure
- Bacterial and viral infections (14,15)
- Cigarette smoking (16,17)
- High caloric/low fiber nutrition
- Obesity [(BMI) ≥ 25 kg/m²] [REF]
- Chronic mucosal or periodontal disease (18–20).

3. Synonyms / lay terms for the event

- Juvenile rheumatoid arthritis
- Juvenile idiopathic arthritis (JIA)

4. Diagnostic entities that may mimic the event or differential diagnosis

- Osteoarthritis (OA)
- Psoriatic arthritis (PsA).
- Others inflammatory immune disease
- Gout, Calcium Pyrophosphate Deposition (CPPD)
- Reactive arthritis
- Septic arthritis

5. Diagnostic tests that are specific for the event

Diagnostic tests specific for RA flares are not defined, as the worsening of the disease is evaluated through the general tests used for RA such as(1,3,21):

- **Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI)**
- **Ultrasound**
- **X-rays** (from identification of joint pain to diagnosis of osteopenia, joint space narrowing, erosion of cartilage and bone):
 - o Stage 1: No destructive changes on X-rays
 - o Stage 2: Presence of X-ray evidence of periarticular osteoporosis, subchondral bone destruction but no joint deformity
 - o Stage 3: X-ray evidence of cartilage and bone destruction in addition to joint deformity and periarticular osteoporosis
 - o Stage 4: Presence of bony or fibrous ankylosis along with stage 3 features
- **Computed tomography (CT) scanning**
- **Positron emission tomography (PET) scan**
- **Bone scan**
- **Dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry (DEXA)**

6. Laboratory test that are specific for the event (3,22)

Laboratory tests specific for RA flares are not defined, as the worsening of the disease is evaluated through the general tests used for RA such as:

- **Rheumatoid factor (RF)** [antibody, positivity, blood test]
- **Anti-cyclic citrullinated peptide antibody (anti-CCP)** [antibody, positivity, blood test]
- **Complete blood count** [anemia, blood test] (22)
- **Erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR or sed rate)** [inflammation, blood test]
- **C-reactive protein (CRP)** [inflammation, blood test]:
- **Other blood tests** (kidney function, electrolytes, liver function, thyroid function, muscle markers, other autoimmune markers, and markers of infection).

Considering the pediatric population, the diagnosis of JIA is made clinically, although there are some biochemical markers (23):

- **RF:** in pediatric patients, its absence does not rule out the disease; this marker is not useful for diagnosis, although it is useful for the classification of JIA under the International League of Associations for Rheumatology (ILAR) criteria.
- **Antinuclear antibodies (ANAs)** increased titters.

7. Medicinal products that are used to treat the event (1,3)

List of RA Medicinal products:

- **Non-steroidal Anti-inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs)** [management of inflammation]:
 - indomethacin
 - piroxicam
 - meloxicam
 - naproxen
 - celecoxib
 - nabumetone

- **Corticosteroids:** [decrease inflammation, pain relief, slow joint damage, bridge therapy Intra-articular for single-joint flares] (9):
 - prednisone 2.5 to 7.5 mg daily to maintain control of RA disease.
 - Higher doses (e.g., 25-50 mg/day) may be used to treat RA flare-ups (24,25).
 - In pediatric population, oral prednisone can be administered at lower dosage than adults (low dose: 0.5mg/kg/day; high dose 2mg/kg/day) (26).

- **Disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs (DMARDs)** [slow/change the progression of the disease] (1):
 - **Conventional Nonbiologic or Synthetic DMARDs (csDMARDs):**
 - Methotrexate, initial drug of choice for RA adult patients:
 - initial dose of 10-15 mg/week,
 - escalation of 5 mg/month.
 - target dose of 20-25 mg/week.
 - Pediatric population (JIA): dose of 10–15 mg/m²/week is recommended.
 - Hydroxychloroquine
 - Sulfasalazine
 - Leflunomide
 - **Targeted synthetic DMARDs (ts-DMARDs):**
 - **Janus kinase (JAK) inhibitors**
 - Tofacitinib
 - Baricitinib
 - Upadacitinib
 - Filgotinib
 - **Biologic response modifiers (bDMARDs)** [if RA does not respond to initial therapies]:

- **Anti-TNF-alpha inhibitors**
 - Etanercept
 - Infliximab
 - Adalimumab
 - Golimumab
 - Certolizumab pegol
- **interleukin (IL) 6 inhibitors**
 - Tocilizumab
 - Sarilumab
- **IL1 inhibitors:**
 - Anakinra
- **T-cell costimulation inhibitors:**
 - Rituximab (anti-CD20 B-cell depleting monoclonal antibody)
 - Abatacept (CTLA4-Ig)

RA and RA Flares Treatment Guidelines (ACR/EULAR) (9,21):

- patients should start DMARD therapy regardless of the disease activity level.
- monotherapy with methotrexate is the preferred treatment, regardless of the disease activity level
- Leflunomide or sulfasalazine are the first-line treatment if contraindication to methotrexate.
- If DMARD monotherapy fail: dual DMARD therapy, a TNF inhibitor, a non-TNF biologic agent, or tofacitinib therapy can be added.
- If disease activity remains high on TNF inhibitor monotherapy, DMARD therapy should be added in addition to the TNF inhibitor.
- If disease activity remains high despite a TNF inhibitor switch to a non-TNF biologic agent with or without methotrexate
- If disease activity remains high despite a trial of anti-TNF and non-TNF agents, use another non-TNF biologic agent before considering JAK.
- If still uncontrolled despite the above trials, use JAK.
- If disease activity remains high despite the above combination therapies, short-term low-dose glucocorticoid therapy should be added.
- TNF inhibitors should be avoided in patients with congestive heart failure.
- Patients with hepatitis C who have not been treated or are currently not in treatment for it should receive nonbiologic DMARD therapy rather than TNF inhibitors.

8. Procedures used to treat the event

- Joint Aspirations
- Injections
- Synovectomy
- Tendon repair
- Joint debridement
- Arthrodesis
- Arthroplasty
- Osteotomy
- Cervical spine surgery

9. Setting (outpatient specialist, in-hospital, GP, emergency room) where the condition will be most frequently /reliably diagnosed.

- In- and out-patient visits
- hospitalization
- emergency room visits
- GP

10. Background rates

No specific rates for RA flares are reported. However, different studies widely reported the incidence and prevalence of RA, independently of its disease activity. A systematic review of population-based studies (including 60 studies) reported a worldwide period prevalence of RA of 0.51% (1955-2015). RA prevalence was higher in North America and Europe and lower in Asia and South America (27). The annual incidence of RA in the United States and other western nations of northern Europe is about 40 per 100,000 persons (28). RA is more prevalent in women compared to men, with a lifetime risk of RA of 3.6% in women compared to 1.7% in men (29). RA risk also increases with age, with a peak incidence between age 65 to 80 years of age (30,31). The risk of RA with a first-degree relative positive for RA is three-fold higher than a second-degree relative with RA giving a two-fold higher risk (32). The strongest genetic predisposition for RA is from the HLA-DRB1 region (shared epitope) (33).

Juvenile idiopathic arthritis (JIA) is the most common chronic rheumatic disease in childhood, affecting one to 4 of every 1000 children worldwide (23).

11. Diagnosis codes or algorithms used to retrieve the event in reference literature

Not Available (NA) for RA flares

12. Code list

No specific codes have been found for RA flares.

13. Algorithm proposal

Based on the OMERACT definition of RA flare and EULAR recommendations (7,9,10), the suggested algorithms for flares identification are:

A code for **RA disease**, **AND**, at least 90 days after:

- Identification of a code indicating a relapse of symptoms (only for SNOMED-based codes), **OR**
- Any initiation, change or increase in therapy (generally in the order as shown below, but not always), **OR**:

1. Non-steroidal Anti-inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs)
2. Corticosteroids
3. Disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs (DMARDs)
 - a. Conventional Nonbiologic or Synthetic DMARDs (csDMARDs)
 - b. Targeted synthetic DMARDs (ts-DMARDs)
 - i. Janus kinase (JAK) inhibitors
 - c. Biologic response modifiers (bDMARDs)
 - i. Anti-TNF-alpha inhibitors
 - ii. interleukin (IL) 6 inhibitors
 - iii. T-cell costimulation inhibitors

- A code of RA complications (with 90 days of wash out period (34)), **OR**:

RA complications list (selected the most specific events from section 1 – “Event definition”):

< Joint inflammation with radiographic damage/deformity/functional disability/scleritis, carpal tunnel syndrome, cervical myelopathy, anemia and Felty syndrome, secondary form of Sjögren

- syndrome, rheumatoid vasculitis, pleuritis, pericarditis, premature death, accelerated rheumatoid nodulosis >
- Any emergency room visit or hospitalization for rheumatologic cause as primary diagnosis.

14. Limitations

No previous studies nor guidelines for identification and estimation of RA flares through electronic healthcare data sources are available.

Missing information about medicines dosage may impact accuracy on identifying cases of RA flares.

Short duration (e.g., 14 days) of RA flares may be also difficult to be identified by electronic healthcare data sources.

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Polyarteritis nodosa flare

Event Definition Form

Event: Polyarteritis nodosa (PAN) flare-up

Outcome/covariate: Outcome

Version: 0.2

Status:

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1. Objective

This event definition form aims to provide an operationalizable definition to detect a flare-up of polyarteritis nodosa in electronic healthcare record databases to conduct epidemiologic research.

2. Event definition

Polyarteritis nodosa (PAN) definition

Polyarteritis nodosa is a rare form of necrotizing non-granulomatous inflammation occurring primarily in medium-sized arteries, often with microaneurysms. PAN is not associated with antineutrophil-cytoplasmic antibodies (ANCA). It is characterized by muscle, joint, and abdominal pain resulting from arterial infarction and scarring in affected organs, and neurological and cutaneous symptoms (1). Vascular inflammation leads to microaneurysm formation, aneurysmal rupture with haemorrhage, thrombosis, and, consequently, organ ischaemia or infarction. There are three clinical subclasses of PAN: (a) cutaneous PAN, (b) hepatitis B virus (HBV)-associated PAN, and (c) idiopathic generalised PAN. Cutaneous PAN can progress to idiopathic generalised PAN (3). Risk factors for PAN disease are HBV, HIV, Hepatitis C, Myelodysplastic syndrome, Chronic myelomonocytic leukemia, Varicella zoster and CKD (4,5).

Flares in PAN

A common and accepted definition of PAN flares is not available, and heterogeneity around the definition of PAN relapses is present, often directly associated with flare identifications.

These are the most used PAN relapse definitions:

- relapse is defined as the reappearance of disease manifestations attributable to active vasculitis occurring after at least one-month symptom-free period (6,7). Remission is defined as the absence of disease activity. Active disease is qualified by the need for ongoing stable maintenance of immunosuppressive therapy (6).
- relapse is defined as the recurrence of clinical signs or symptoms, or the occurrence of new symptoms [Paediatric Vasculitis Activity Score (PVAS) >0], after a prior sustained symptoms remission of 3 months, requiring the resumption of immunosuppressive therapy or the reinstatement of corticosteroids (dosage increased by >50% to >0.5 mg/kg/day). Remission is defined as the absence of any clinical signs/symptoms of active vasculitis, as supported by

laboratory evidence of normal C Reactive Protein (CRP) and Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate (ESR) values, and a PVAS of 0 of 63 (assigned retrospectively for every clinic visit), for 2 evaluations at least 1 month apart and with adherence to the prednisolone regimen (8).

- cutaneous polyarteritis nodosa (CPAN) relapse is defined as the first reoccurrence or new onset of cutaneous disease that requires further escalation of treatment with prednisone at a dosage of more than 20 mg/d and/or additional use of immunosuppressants observed more than 6 months after the initial therapy (9).
- relapse is defined as the occurrence of one of the following events: (i) general symptoms (i.e. malaise, fever, weight loss, myalgia, arthralgia) in conjunction with a rise in CRP, when infection and other causes were ruled out; (ii) gastrointestinal or renal infarction or bleeding from aneurysms, as seen at surgery or strongly suspected by angiography; (iii) new mononeuritis multiplex; (iv) a rapid rise in serum creatinine levels and blood pressure; (v) testicular pain; (vi) skin vasculitis; and (vii) uveitis, when (i–vii) were considered to be due to vasculitis (10).

3. Synonyms / lay terms for the event

- Periarteritis Nodosa
- Necrotizing Arteritis
- Arteritides, Necrotizing
- Arteritis, Necrotizing
- Necrotizing Arteritides
- Essential Polyarteritis
- Essential Polyarteritides
- Polyarteritides, Essential
- Polyarteritis, Essential

4. Diagnostic entities that may mimic the event or differential diagnosis

Churg-Strauss Syndrome, Deficiency of adenosine deaminase-2 (ADA2), Wegener's granulomatosis or granulomatosis with polyangiitis (ICD9-CM 446.4) (11).

5. Diagnostic tests that are specific for the event

To achieve the maximal diagnostic efficiency, biopsies must be performed on symptomatic sites (e.g. muscle, sural nerve, skin, or testicle) (3,12).

6. Laboratory test that are specific for the event

Laboratory tests specific for PAN flares are not defined, as the worsening or the activity of the disease is evaluated through the general tests used for PAN (12-14), such as:

- Erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) and/or C-reactive protein (CRP) (do not correlate with disease activity in all patients).
- Leukocytosis, normochromic anemia, or thrombocytosis.
- Hepatitis B surface antigen and hepatitis C serologies.
- Creatinine level.
- Mild proteinuria.
- Levels of liver enzymes.
- Markers of renal functions and urine test.
- Hypergammaglobulinemia (13).

7. Medicinal products that are used to treat the event

List of PAN Medicinal products:

Newly diagnosed non-severe idiopathic generalised PAN cases:

- Glucocorticoids (alone) [induction and maintenance of therapeutic regimen]
 - o Prednisone 1mg/kg/day with subsequent tapering off over 9–12 months.
- Corticosteroids followed by plasmapheresis and antiviral agents [only for hepatitis B–related PAN] (16).

Mild forms of PAN or CPAN:

- Non-steroidal Anti-inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs)
- Topical corticosteroids
- Dapsone
- Glucocorticoids (alone) [induction and maintenance of therapeutic regimen]

Moderate-to-severe idiopathic generalized PAN:

- Glucocorticoids (alone) [induction and maintenance of therapeutic regimen]
- Combination of glucocorticoid and cyclophosphamide
- Intravenous cyclophosphamide of 600 mg/m² (every 2 weeks/3 doses, then every 4 weeks for 4 months)
- Intravenous cyclophosphamide of 15 mg/kg (at weeks 0, 2 and 4, then every 3 weeks)
- Rituximab after methylprednisolone pulse therapy [if patient is refractory to cyclophosphamide]
- Intravenous immunoglobulin (IVIG) [if patient is refractory to cyclophosphamide] (15).

Sever forms of PAN or CPAN, as well as refractory to glucocorticoid alone, recalcitrant lesions or relapsing course, may led to the use of (19):

- Oral corticosteroids
- Methotrexate
- Azathioprine
- Mycophenolate mofetil
- Other immunosuppressants

Children with PAN, the treatment is individualized:

- Glucocorticoids [to reduce inflammation]:
 - o High-dose intravenous pulse methylprednisolone (1 hour with monitoring blood pressure to treat organ- or life-threatening disease, repeated daily for 3-6 days).
- Cytotoxic drugs (lifesaving conditions)
- Plasma exchange therapy (with or without hemodialysis)

8. Procedures used to treat the event

- Plasma exchanges
- Surgery of gastrointestinal (GI) PAN manifestations (e.g., bowel ischemia, cholecystitis, appendicitis)
- Microcoil embolization of cerebral aneurysm
- Postsurgical care for bowel infarction (20).

9. Setting (outpatient specialist, in-hospital, GP, emergency room) where the condition will be most frequently /reliably diagnosed.

- In- and out-patient visits
- hospitalization
- emergency room visits
- GP

10. Background rates

Different studies widely reported the incidence and prevalence of PAN, which overall varies from 0.2 to 7.7 cases per 100,000 depending on the used definition, populations and regions. Men are generally more affected by PAN than women (male-to-female ratio 1.6-2:1). PAN is diagnosed at every age, predominantly in 45-65 years old individuals (21). Children likely have milder cutaneous PAN compared to adults.

The course of CPAN disease is more often chronic and relapsing (45.2%) than that of systemic PAN (9.2%) (20). The relapse rate of HBV-associated PAN is lower than the other types (6). In children, the PAN relapse rate is reported to be around 35% (21).

11. Diagnosis codes or algorithms used to retrieve the event in reference literature

Not Available (NA) for PAN flares

12. Code list

No specific codes have been found for PAN flares.

13. Algorithm proposal

A code for PAN disease **AND**, at least 90 days after:

- Switch from a corticosteroid to another immunosuppressant, e.g. cyclophosphamide, **OR**
- change in dosages [Immunosuppressant **OR** Corticosteroid dosage increased by 50% or more in compared to previous treatment **OR** increases in the dose of corticosteroid to 0.5 mg/kg/day and more], **OR**
- Identification of a code indicating a relapse of symptoms (only for SNOMED-based codes), **OR**
- Recurrence of clinical manifestation or the occurrence of new symptoms attributable to active vasculitis occurring after at least a three-month symptom-free period (occurrence of one of the following: (i) general symptoms, i.e. malaise, fever, weight loss, myalgia, arthralgia, in conjunction with a rise in CRP, when infection and other causes were ruled out; (ii) gastrointestinal or renal infarction or bleeding from aneurysms, as seen at surgery or strongly suspected by angiography; (iii) new mononeuritis multiplex; (iv) a rapid rise in serum creatinine levels and blood pressure; (v) testicular pain; (vi) skin vasculitis; and (vii) uveitis, when (i–vii) were considered to be due to vasculitis), **OR**
- A claim for a hospitalization or emergency room visit with a primary diagnosis of PAN.

14. Limitation

Some clinical manifestations that have been included in the algorithm proposal may not be specifically linked to vasculitis and could be not considered for the final identification of the flares if unspecific.

Moreover, change in dosage may not be detectable in some data sources, which may lead to an underestimation of the flares' incidence.

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